

De La Salle University – Dasmariñas
GRADUATE PROGRAM

**THE DIFFICULTIES ENCOUNTERED BY GRADE 11 STUDENTS IN THE
LEARNING COMPETENCIES OF PRACTICAL RESEARCH 1**

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GRETTA NAVALES

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Abstract

Practical Research 1 is one of the compulsory subjects in Grade 11 senior high school under the K to 12 Curriculum. Considering the fact that Grade 11 students have little to no experience about research writing, this study determined the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 and the factors that contribute to the difficulties. Also, it further examined the significant difference in the difficulties encountered by students in terms of their sex, socio-economic status, and strand; and the proposed helpful recommendations and instructional model to respond to the identified difficulties. This study was conducted at the University of Makati, Senior High School Department, with the sample size of 474 Grade 11 student respondents and 20 teacher respondents. It is a descriptive quantitative study which employed online survey in data collection. Accordingly, the findings revealed that Grade 11 students encountered scientific and language difficulties in the 14 out of 36 learning competencies of Practical Research 1, specifically in the 1) *oral presentation of the written research report*, 2) *finalizing the research output*, 3) *knowing the search process*, 4) *selecting relevant literature*, 5) *writing coherent review of literature*, 6) *presenting vast review*, 7) *synthesizing information from relevant literature*, 8) *relating the research findings with pertinent literature*, 9) *writing the research methodology*, 10) *planning data collection and analysis procedures*, 11) *utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output*, 12) *drawing conclusions from patterns and themes*, 13) *describing characteristics of research*, and 14) *creating patterns and themes from data*. The specific difficulties in each of the learning competency appeared to be associated with the following factors: *teaching instructions, complexity of research parts, time constraint, insufficient resources, language skills, lack of cooperation from group members, and data gathering*. Moreover, it appeared that there was significant difference in the encountered difficulties of students between strands. In light of the findings, the teaching instructions and curriculum guide in Practical Research 1 must be revisited by the teacher, curriculum developers, and school to address the identified difficulties encountered by students and the factors that contribute to the difficulties. Therefore, the study proposed the utilization of direct instruction, scientific and language needs assessment, and subject integration in teaching Practical Research 1 as strategies to help students cope with the identified difficulties.

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Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

K to 12 Program started in the Philippines in the school year 2016-2017 under Republic Act 10533 or Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. The additional 2 years in senior high school is part of the program to enhance the quality of education in the country. The senior high school program offers 4 different tracks that the students may choose upon enrolment, namely: 1) Academic Track, which includes the following strands: Science, Technology, Engineering & Mathematics (STEM), Accountancy, Business, & Management (ABM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), and General Academic Strand (GAS); 2) Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track (TVL), which includes the following strands: Animation (ANM), Automotive (AUT), Computer Programming (CPG), Computer System Services (CSS), Electrical Installation and Maintenance (EIM), Electronics Products Assembly and Services (ELP), Drafting (DFT), Hotel and Restaurant Services (HRS), and Tourism (TRM); 3) Sports Track; and 4) Arts and Design Track, which includes the following strands: Dance (DNC), Theater (THR), Film (FLM), and Music (MSC). Before its mandatory implementation in the year 2016, the government selected the University of Makati, specifically the Higher School ng UMak (HSU) Department, to pilot test the program in the year 2012. The University of Makati is the pioneer senior high school that produced more than three thousand Grade 12 graduates, the first and largest

senior high school graduates during the school year 2012-2013 (Rappler, 2014). This school has been offering the complete 4 tracks with its admission policies since 2012. Thus, the qualification of students in the Academic Track would be determined by their Grade 10 general weighted average (GWA). The aspiring student must have $GWA \geq 85\%$ and $Grades \geq 80\%$ to be qualified in STEM Strand, a $GWA \geq 84\%$ and $Grades \geq 80\%$ for ABM Strand, and $GWA \geq 83\%$ for HUMSS Strand. On the other hand, there is no grade requirement upon in any Non-Academic Tracks such as Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track (TVL), Sports Track, and Arts and Design Track (University of Makati, 2020). The present senior high school curriculum applies competency-based education that enables students to progress in differentiated and directed instruction. Competency-Based Education (CBE) refers to the systems of instruction, assessment, grading, and academic reporting based on the students' demonstration of their mastery of the expected learning competencies. The learning competencies are the main ideas or skills that are expected to be mastered by the students (Gosselin, 2019). The general goal of Competency-Based Education is to ensure that students acquire and demonstrate the knowledge and skills essential to succeed in school, higher education, and future career by engaging in the learning exercises, activities, and experiences that are aligned with clearly defined outcomes (Understanding Competency-Based Education, 2017). Besides, in the study Azinmov et al. as cited in Makulova (2015), 'competency' is defined as a combination of knowledge, skills, and

abilities formed in the process of learning a particular discipline, as well as the ability to perform any activity based on the acquired learning competencies. For the students to achieve competency, they should first understand the learning objectives for them to focus on what they need to know and to efficiently show what they ought to perform (Deye, 2017). Because of this, the senior high school curriculum has differentiated clusters of subjects and each subject has target learning competencies and objectives. The varied subjects are clustered into three: the core subjects, applied subjects, and specialized subjects. The specialized subjects are considered as the major courses particular to a certain strand and focus on the field of specialization. Conversely, the core subjects and the applied subjects are subjects that should be taken by all senior high school students regardless of their strand; however, the core subjects contain the general or basic information while the applied subjects have complex topics which the conduct might vary from one strand to another.

Practical Research 1 has complex topics because it is an applied subject. Certainly, research is an integral part of education since it covers several learning areas such as language and scientific learning competencies. A research paper as an output is a form of academic writing in which the students comply as one a requirement for a particular subject. Research involves scientific and language learning competencies. The scientific learning competencies of the research course include evaluation and planning of research

methodology, data collection, interpretation, analysis, etc. while the language learning competencies entail academic writing strategies such as writing citations, synthesis, summary, conclusion, and references that would help students improve their scientific and language literacy (Litsyani, 2018). Research requires extensive readings of literature since it is a scholarly undertaking (Lee, 2014). Conversely, the senior high school program has two major research subjects. First is Practical Research 1, which is Qualitative Research that should be taken by Grade 11 students. Second is the Practical Research 2, which is Quantitative Research that should be accomplished by Grade 12 students. Practical Research 1 is intended to develop the scientific and language literacy of Grade 11 students. As stated by the Department of Education (2016), research subjects primarily aim to develop scientific skills such as critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Moreover, learning research involves complex performances such as understanding, preparing, conducting, writing, and presenting research output. Thus, there is a curriculum guide that comprises of content and guidelines for teaching research in senior high school developed by the Department of Education (DepEd). Research teachers are provided with the curriculum guide that consists of the course content, content and performance standard, and learning competencies. The learning competencies in the curriculum guide are mostly scientific and language based. These research learning competencies are anchored to CBE; however, the language learning competencies are under Competency-based Language

Teaching (CBLT), which is a specified approach for language teaching and learning that is outlined from the principles of CBE (Richards, 2020). The CBLT involves expected language competencies and helpful assessment in teaching language to students; hence, at the end of the course, the students are expected to demonstrate the learning competencies. The role of the teacher is to identify what particular learning competencies are successfully achieved and struggled with. Along the learning process, teachers should be able to determine the difficulty encountered by the students concerning the learning competencies considering the factors that could affect the learning process such as economic, social, environmental, and linguistic (Khatoon et al., 2011). Specifically, the learning competencies are the list of knowledge or skills that the students should master in the course which are written on the curriculum guide while the difficulties refer to the particular aspect of competencies which are found difficult to perform by students. Thus, if the students do not demonstrate adequate proficiency because of the difficulties they encounter in the learning competencies, they must be provided with supports and interventions to help them overcome the learning difficulties (Deye, 2017). Many of Grade 11 students experience troubles with their academic performances since their subjects are different compared to what they had in junior high school (Atencio, 2021). Grade 11 students are still in the process of revising their former concrete thinking into fuller understanding of principles as they transcend the basic knowledge in junior high school

and try to decipher the complex concepts in senior high school (Manitoba Education & Training, 2020). Hence, the students' difficulty in mastering the learning competencies of the subject is quite inevitable. Learning difficulty is an umbrella term for academic problems of different origins. It comprises of general learning deficits and low academic performance (Lenhard, 2018). According to different studies, there are learning difficulties that can be helpful or distractive to the students' learning process. Based on the findings of Alter et al. (2007), students learn to create a more systematic or analytic approach to the material when they encounter difficulties in learning. Learning difficulties act as confusion activators for the students to create a more critical learning strategy that leaves remarkable learning benefits to the students. In contrast, Lodge (2018) stated that confusion-inducing difficulties are not a constructive part of the learning process. This means that when students encounter confusion-inducing difficulties, they are more likely to have low academic performance compared to less confused students. For instance, when students are tasked to write a research introduction, the students who do not experience confusion-inducing difficulty in the task might produce better output than those who experience difficulty in the task. As stated by Ajzen (1985) in his theory of behavioral intention, there is so-called "perceived difficulty", which is conceptualized as the perception of students of the ease or difficulty of performing a specific activity. The students' perception of difficulty affects their learning performance. So, if the task is perceived to be difficult, then students

expect that their chance of success is low, which may contribute to failure due to difficulty. Furthermore, students who encounter learning difficulties are less likely to master the learning competencies (Lodge, 2018). On the other hand, teacher could help students cope with the difficulties they encounter by identifying the difficulties and providing appropriate support to students in the learning process. Teacher observation on the students learning performance and difficulties has been accepted readily in the past as valid source of information for recording and reporting students' demonstration of the learning competencies. The teacher observation serves as evidence which could accurately represent the observed students' performance (Maxwell, 2001). Since teachers have the first-hand experience and observation on the students' performance, their perception about the difficulties encountered by students in the course is considered reliable. Though there are contrasting pieces of evidence about learning difficulties under different situations, the present study focused on the identification of the confusion-inducing difficulties that could hinder the students' acquisition of the expected learning competencies.

The difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies in Practical Research 1 might vary according to their strand, sex, and economic status. There are observable learning differences between strands; the students' admission in the academic strands entails specified grade requirements, which somehow indicates academic competency, unlike the non-academic strands which have no grade requirement upon

admission. Consequently, students from the academic track are more likely to cope with the expected learning competencies because of their positive attitudes towards academic and scientific involvement (Gallos, 2018) while students from the non-academic track are observed to have difficulties in coping with academic matters because of their negative attitude towards academic involvement (Houtte & Stevens, 2009). The relationship of a person's attitude towards doing the task was mentioned by Ajzen (1985) in his theory of behavioral intention in which he stated that if the person has a low intention or negative attitude, it might be due to underlying factors. For instance, if the students have a negative perception of doing a research task, the underlying factors could be a lack of practice or knowledge in science or language literacy. In addition, accomplishing research tasks or acquiring the learning competencies in research might be advantageous to the academic strands because the major subjects of academic strands are broadly theoretical or scientific knowledge while the non-academic strand is mostly skill-based.

Moreover, there are research findings that discuss the relationship of sex to students' science and academic literacy which are the needed skills in research writing. Sex refers to the biological aspects of an individual generally assigned as male or female at birth (Tolland & Evans, 2019). It is one of the factors that shape students' scientific and language skills. It is a sociocultural factor that affects the language learning process including writing (Kamiar et al., 2012, as cited in Bijami, 2013). As reported by Peterson (2000), female

shows superiority in writing than male through great details and conformity to writing conventions. In the Epistemological Reflection Model of Severiens (1998), it is noted that males and females have different ways of reasoning and knowing. The women's pattern of reasoning focuses on "relational aspects" which seems to incorporate other perspectives while the men's reasoning is more of "individual focus" which only considers their perspective. This means that women are more passive in knowing things than men and they construct their perspectives by interacting with others while men independently construct and expand answers. Male and female also speak and write differently using different language features due to the difference between their reasoning and thinking ability, (Soori & Zamani, 2011). There are also identified differences between sex and mastery of scientific literacy such as recognizing scientific questions, identifying evidence, communicating the conclusion, and demonstrating understanding of the concept. Female is more likely to master the scientific skills while male mastery is limited to concluding (Kristyasari et al, 2018). Furthermore, there is a significant difference in the subject preference between different sexes and the difference becomes diverse when they enter high school. Male prefers mathematics and female prefers literature. The subject preference makes a measurable difference in boys' and girls' academic performance (Seifert & Sutton, 2009). It is also supported by O'Dea et al. (2018) who stated that sex differences in grade variability of students are strongly affected by the subject. This means that when students

prefer the subject or topic, they show a higher interest in it more than the less preferred subject. Sex has been frequently one of the variables in every pedagogical study which has something to do with the learning attitude and performance of students. Hence, the present study is expected to identify whether sex is contributory to the difficulties encountered by students in accomplishing the learning competencies in the research subject.

Another factor that elicits learning difficulties and differences is socio-economic status of students. Socio-economic status (SES) is defined by American Psychological Association (2020) as the social standing or class of an individual or group. It is often measured as a combination of education, income, and occupation. Based on the Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES) in 2017, cited by Albert et al. (2018), the following socio-economic classes are categorized according to the range of monthly family incomes for a family size of 5 members: 1) Poor, who gains less than PHP 9,520 per month, 2) Low income but not poor, who gains between PHP 9,520 to PHP 19,040 per month, 3) Lower middle income, who gains between PHP 19,040 to PHP 38,080 per month, 4) Middle income class, who gains between PHP 38,080 to PHP 66,640 per month, 5) Upper middle income, who gains Between PHP 66,640 to PHP 109,200 per month, 6) Upper income but not rich, who gains between PHP 114,240 to PHP 190,400 per month, and 7) Rich, who gains at least PHP 190,400 per month. According to the findings of Dolek & Hamzadayi (2018), both students with high or low SES experience difficulty in writing, specifically in

organizing ideas and providing support to the thesis. However, there are also findings of the significant difference between learning performance of students and different SES. Conferring to the study of Bhat et al. (2016), students with high socio-economic status have high academic achievement than students with low socio-economic status and concluded that there is a significant difference in the achievement of students between high and low socio-economic classes. As elaborated by Jensen (2013), people from different socio-economic classes have varied lifestyles, vocabulary, cognition, effort, and growth mindset. Thus, the students' language partly depends on the complexity of the language transmitted by the family, which is also affected by lifestyle (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1990, as cited in Turmo, 2004). Consequently, social status affects the students' learning and academic performance because it affects their way of living. In a language study, it is elaborated that students of high SES are more successful than those who have low SES in some dimensions of writing skills such as form, content, word choice, organization, and grammar (Dolek & Hamzadayi, 2018). In a scientific literacy study, there is a large difference in the scientific achievement between students with high and low SES. It means that scientific skills are better adapted by students with high SES than students with low SES (Turmo, 2004).

The learning competencies in Practical Research 1 are expected to be acquired and demonstrated by students to develop their scientific and academic literacy. However, some research findings have revealed that students encounter difficulty in accomplishing and

demonstrating the learning competencies of research, specifically the scientific and language competencies of research. Although students are normally familiar with the basic writing skills such as punctuation, grammar, spelling, and word choice (Pablo & Lasaten, 2019), there are features of research writing or academic writing that they perceive difficult to perform such as citation, paraphrasing, and summarizing. Based on a study, inappropriate citing is tied to students' confusion of how to do the proper citation, underdeveloped reading comprehension, and critical thinking (Bloch, 2012, as cited in Fazilatfar et al., 2018). In the findings of Campbell (1990, as cited in Fazilatfar et al., 2018), it is stated that some second language learners encounter difficulties in paraphrasing and summarizing while other study identified that students in Asia have limited exposure to writing citation, paraphrase, and summary, which leads to difficulty in the actual writing process (Keck, 2014). Moreover, Sumardi (2019) stated in his study that Grade 11 students have difficulties in writing academic essays and have poor to fair writing skills specifically in maintaining logical organization, good grammar, formality, and vocabulary. Also, he identified that Grade 11 students have difficulty in choosing appropriate words to use in writing, spelling, and vocabulary. Additionally, since research requires intensive and comprehensive reading, the students' critical reading skills could be greatly useful in selecting relevant literature for the present study, but the findings of Georgiou (2015) revealed that some Grade 11 students have poor critical reading skills. Aside from the

academic writing challenges, some studies have identified that students have difficulties in the oral presentation. Students have initial anxiety in oral presentation due to some factors including language skills; oral presentation could be affected by poor language skills such as vocabulary deficiency and difficulty in reading (Mclean et al., 2013; Al- Nouh et al., 2015). However, on the scientific competencies of research, students view the basic principles of research as challenging (Gallos, 2018). According to Murtonen & Lehtiner (2003), students who enroll in research courses have high anxiety in understanding research methodologies and principles, which results to failure in learning and demotivation to pursue the research output. Muhammad (2019) stated that students have lack of familiarity with the format and process of research, which triggers the difficulty encountered by students. For novice researchers, deciding the methodology of a research paper can be an overwhelming process, especially considering the complex elements covered by this research section (Ellis & Levy, 2009). Turning to the process of data collection, according to Dearnley (as cited in Remando et al., 2015), student researchers encounter challenges in conducting data collection especially in convincing the respondents or participants. Also, analysis and organizing results are indeed very challenging processes for students; thus, they need to practice step-by-step procedure in analyzing qualitative data (Wang, 2013). The afore-mentioned difficulties encountered by students could make them uninterested and struggling in learning and making research papers. It could affect the quality and

submission of their output (Lee, 2018). Though there are cited literatures about the difficulties encountered by students in research, most of the are from foreign context and are not particularized according to the challenges encountered by students in the scientific and language learning competencies of Practical Research 1, which is realistically from the DepEd curriculum guide. Thus, to respond to this concern, the researcher aimed to scrutinize the encountered difficulties of students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 and to divulge the factors that contribute to the difficulties. Moreover, the information about the difficulties encountered by senior high school students in research subject is very limited since it is just a new subject in the K to 12 Curriculum; thus, findings about the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in Practical Research 1 are relevantly needed.

At present, the learning competencies listed in the Practical Research 1 curriculum guide are mostly scientific and language focused. These competencies are needed to be taught by the teacher and to be demonstrated by the Grade 11 students. Consequently, it is necessary to determine the difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of research to help them overcome the underlying challenges and to go back to the general goal of competency-based education which is to ensure that the students acquire the knowledge and skills essential to success in school, higher education, and future career (Understanding Competency-Based Education, 2017). Thus, the researcher became

interested to identify the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 which are mostly about scientific and language difficulties and also the factors that contribute to the difficulties. Moreover, this study further examined if there is significant difference in the difficulties encountered by students in terms of their sex, socio-economic status, and strand. Subsequently, the findings of this study may help improve the course content, content standard, performance standard, and learning competencies of the Practical Research 1 curriculum guide. Also, it could lead to helpful recommendations and instructional model to help students cope with the difficulties they encounter in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1.

Furthermore, the present study was meant to understand the experience of Grade 11 students in undertaking research, specifically the difficulties they encounter in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. The findings of this study could be primarily beneficial to the:

1. Students who encounter difficulties in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. Relevant recommendations and instructional model could be proposed in this study which may help the students to cope with the encountered difficulties.
2. Teachers who need to know the encountered difficulties of students in the learning competencies of research which would enable them to adjust their

instruction and lesson emphasis considering the identified factors that contribute to the difficulties encountered by students.

3. Curriculum Guide Developers who may consider the encounter difficulties of students in the learning competencies of research as to sex, socio-economic status, and strand may use the major findings for the possible revision or modification of the content of Practical Research 1 curriculum guide.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 at the University of Makati. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of Grade 11 students as to:
 - 1.1 sex,
 - 1.2 socio-economic status, and
 - 1.3 strand,
2. What are the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 and the factors that contribute to the difficulties?
3. Is there a significant difference in the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 when grouped according to:
 - 3.1 sex,
 - 3.2 socio-economic status, and

3.3 strand?

4. What are the recommendations and the proposed instructional model to help students cope with the difficulties they encounter in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1?

Hypothesis

The hypothesis is tested through 0.05(5%) level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

H₁: There is a significant difference in the encountered difficulties of students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 when grouped according to:

- 3.1 sex,
- 3.2 socio-economic status, and
- 3.3 strand?

H₀: There is no significant difference in the encountered difficulties of students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 when grouped according to:

- 3.1 sex,
- 3.2 socio-economic status, and
- 3.3 strand?

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of a study contains the concepts, definitions, and references to relevant scholarly literature. The research framework must establish an

understanding of theories and principles which are relevant to the present study (University of Southern California, 2020). This, this study links the Competency-Based Language Teaching (CBLT), Competency-Based Education (CBE), and Four Pillars of Learning, and Behavioral Intention Theory of Ajzen (1985) as grounds to understand the difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. Understanding the encountered difficulties is significant to help students succeed in the demonstration of the learning competencies.

Research tends to develop students' applied skills such as academic writing and critical thinking. It employs Bloom's Taxonomy- Revised which is not only limited to 'understanding' and 'memorizing' but includes higher-order cognitive skills which involve 'applying', 'analyzing', 'evaluating', and 'creating' (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). The needed skills in writing research must be observable; thus, learning and teaching research is guided with objectives, course content, performance standard, and reliable assessments to ensure that the desired learning competencies are demonstrated with quality.

The enclosure of learning competencies in the new curriculum is based on the Four Pillars of Learning: Learning to know, Learning to do, Learning to live together, and Learning to be (Delors et al., 1996, as cited in Tawil & Cougoureux, 2013). The four pillars of education should be considered in the curriculum development and content for they play a holistic role in learning. The 'learning to know' ensures the essential development of skill

and knowledge needed by the students; the 'learning to do' guarantees the acquisition of applied skills linked to professional success; the 'learning to live together' warrants the development of social skills and values such as respect and concern for others; and the 'learning to be' contributes to a person's mind, body, and spirit such as sports and arts. Historically, these four pillars of learning have brought multifaceted changes to curriculum and society which have been observed worldwide since 1900s (Delors et al., 1996 as cited by Tawil & Coughoureux, 2013).

Through the improvement of the basic curriculum, senior high school has adapted Competency-Based Education which debunks the traditional ways of learning. Historically, Competency-Based Education was first introduced by John Dewey more than 100 years ago through his 'learning by doing' principle and it was the beginning of turning conventional education into experimentalist education (Waks, 2018). Patterned with Dewey's principle of education, Competency-Based Education focuses on the student's demonstration of the desired learning competencies as the product of the learning process (Understanding Competency-Based Education, 2017). This principle of education can be observed in applied subjects of senior high school where the learning competencies are clearly coded and elaborated. For instance, in Practical Research 1, which is an applied subject, one of the 34 listed learning competencies that a student should master is 'writing research title' which is coded as CS_RS11-IIIc-e-2. Each competency is coded for the

future review of the competencies that are learned and not learned by the student. Students learning experiences must be guided considering that they might encounter difficulty in learning a particular knowledge or skill. Also, educational institutions should ensure to assess and recognize the different learning needs of the students and to give equity of strategies that guarantee that students will receive differentiated instructional support they need. Supporting and knowing the students' learning experiences along the way helps them overcome the learning difficulties they encounter. Hence, the teacher must organize tools and resources based on the learning experiences of students especially when the competencies are not met. Schools that have clear pedagogy will have coherent and more advanced instruction. Based on the Working definition of Competency Education (2011), the concept of Competency-Based Education includes: 1) students advance upon demonstrated mastery; 2) competencies include explicit, measurable, attainable learning objectives that empower students; 3) assessment is meaningful and a positive learning experience for students; 4) students receive timely differentiated support based on their individual learning needs; and 5) learning outcomes emphasize competencies that include application and creation of knowledge, along with the development of important skills and dispositions. Among the 5 notions, the present study highlighted the 2nd and 4th notions specific for analyzing the needed competencies and identifying learning needs. It is important to identify if the given competencies are attainable by students. Also, identifying

the students' learning needs is helpful for them to be given differentiated support. Thus, the study focused on knowing the difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of research and the factors that contribute to the difficulties to provide recommendations on how students could cope with the difficulties.

Language teaching and learning have been challenging throughout the years; therefore, it is important to use different principles that guarantee learning. Competency-Based Language Teaching is one of the language principles applied in modern education. This is an application of the principles of Competency-Based Education (Bataineh & Tasnimi, 2014). As a language teaching approach, CBLT is oriented to the learning objectives, including the macro and micro language competencies (Baturkan, 2006). According to Richards & Rogers (2001), as cited in Montazeri et al. (2014), this language approach focuses on the outcomes of learning and seeks to improve accountability in teaching through connecting instruction to outcomes and performance standards. Thus, the factors that contribute to the effectiveness of its implementation must be considered; these are: useful functioning in society, focus on life skills, performance-centered orientation, modulated instructions, explicit outcomes, continuous assessment, demonstrated mastery of competencies, and student-centered instruction (Auebach, 1986, as cited in Montazeri et al., 2014). Rooted on the competency-based education objectives, CBLT focuses on what a language learner should be able to do at the end of the course (Nunan 2007, as cited in

Montazeri et al., 2014).

As mentioned in the previous paragraphs, learning competencies are the expected knowledge or skills which are necessary to be demonstrated by the students after the learning instructions. Another example of the learning competencies listed in the Practical Research curriculum guide is synthesizing information from relevant literature”. According to the set learning competencies, the students must be able to write related literature and synthesize it. But students might have a different perception of the difficulty of task that might affect their performance in accomplishing it. Some students find writing related literature as a difficult task to accomplish because of their underdeveloped ability to cite, paraphrase, and summarize (Bloch, 2012; Campbell, 1990). Based on the theory of Ajzen (1985), there is such drive called “behavioral intention”, which is described as the person's subjective probability that he or she will perform the behavior or task. In the theory, it is stated the "perceived difficulty" affects the behavioral intention of the person. So, if the task is perceived to be difficult, then students expect that their chance of success is low and attribute failure to the encountered difficulties. A low intention in this sense means low effort, and a high intention means high effort. Furthermore, the behavioral intention of students might be influenced by different factors such as expected hindrances or lack of knowledge in doing the task. Hence, students who encounter difficulties in research might be driven by factors and it is necessary to address what those factors are to help the students

cope with the encountered difficulties.

Therefore, competency-based language teaching, competency-based education, and Four 'Pillars of Learning' reiterate the importance of the mastery of expected learning competencies. CBLT is central to the completion of second language competencies. Institutions may use methods of instruction and assessment to determine whether students have achieved competency. If there are learning competencies that will not be met by students, the encountered difficulties based on the Behavioral Intention Theory might be one of the deterring factors and should be revisited so that appropriate intervention may be given. As an educational strategy, competency-based system could provide educators with more detailed information about the strengths and weaknesses of students and could lead to proficient learning as long as the concept and skills that have not yet been mastered will be accommodated.

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework is used to illustrate expected findings by showing the variables of the study and their relationship (Swaen, 2020). Also, it clearly shows the research path and grounds. Thus, this is guided by the theories presented in the theoretical framework.

This study is anchored on the principles of Competency-Based Language Teaching, Competency-Based Education, Four 'Pillars of Learning', and Behavioral Intention Theory

of Ajzen (1985), which are linked to the expected learning competencies in the Practical Research 1 Curriculum Guide of the Department of Education.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study in Schematic Diagram

The diagram presents the research path grounded on the theoretical framework

and the research questions of the study. It illustrates the scope of the study, specifically the relationship of the variables and the expected outcome of the study. Primarily, it presents the connection of the independent and dependent variables. The independent variables in the study are the 36 learning competencies in Practical Research 1 while the dependent variables are the difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of research according to their sex, socio-economic status, and strand; and the factors that contribute to the difficulties. Practical Research 1 is one of the required subjects in Grade 11. The 36 learning competencies of Practical Research 1 in the diagram are based on the curriculum guide provided by DepEd. These learning competencies are the specific knowledge and skills that the students should master in the research course which is comprised of scientific and language competencies. The scientific learning competencies in Practical Research 1 are about identifying research problem, formulating research questions, data collection, analyzing research results, coding, etc. while the language learning competencies are mostly about academic writing such as logical writing, paraphrasing, synthesizing, and citing of research parts. Based on the Working definition of Competency Education (2011), if the afore-mentioned competencies are not met by the students after the lesson, the teacher must organize tools and instructions based on the learning experiences of students. Schools that have clear pedagogy will have coherent and more advanced instruction. Hence, the identification of the specific difficulties encountered

by students and the factors that contribute to the difficulties would improve the teaching instruction that would help the students cope with the difficulties and master the competencies. The general difficulties encountered by students in the 36 learning competencies were primarily identified by the Grade 11 by student respondents and the difficulties were determined through Likert Scale questions in the survey questionnaire. The factors that contributed to the difficulties were also identified by the students through an open-ended question in the survey questionnaire. On the other hand, after the students had identified the general difficulties, the research teachers provided ancillary data about the specific aspects of difficulties to elaborate the initial findings from the student respondents since the research teachers have direct experience and observation on the difficulties encountered by students. When the difficulties and factors were already identified, the significant difference in the difficulties encountered by students according to their sex, socio-economic status, and the strand were subjected to hypothesis testing. The significant difference in the variables sex, socio-economic status, and strand were tested to determine if there would be significant difference in the difficulties encountered by students between sexes, social classes, and strands. The interpretation of the significant difference was supported by the difficulties and factors that contribute to the difficulties encountered by students. Consequently, when the present study had identified the specific difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical

Research 1 and recognized the underlying factors that contribute to it, the output of the study proposed recommendations and instructional model for teaching Practical Research 1 that could help students cope with the difficulties and eventually master the learning competencies of Practical Research 1.

Chapter 2
METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive research design which provided answers to the questions associated with the variables and problem of the study limited to 'what', 'who', 'when', and 'how'; hence, this was quantitative in type. Quantitative research is described as a method of emphasizing the objective measurement and statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of the data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques. Furthermore, quantitative study focuses on gathering numerical data and generalizing it across groups of people or explains a particular phenomenon (Muijs, 2010). Consequently, descriptive quantitative design is defined as a method used to obtain information concerning current status of the phenomena and to describe "what exists" according to the variables or conditions in a situation (Organizing Academic Papers, 2020). The research design was explicitly chosen to fulfil the objectives of the study through the collection and analysis of numerical data from the survey questionnaires. The survey questionnaire comprised of Likert and multiple response questions which were intended to identify the difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. It also contained 1 additional open-ended question to elucidate the factors that contribute to the identified difficulties encountered by students which was then converted into numerical data. The numerical data from the Likert and multiple response questions were analyzed

through descriptive statistics while data from the open-ended question were thematically sorted and converted into numerical data or analyzed through quantitative content analysis, which is defined as a method of identifying patterns or themes then counting their frequency (Luo, 2020). The analyzed data from the open-ended question were used to support the interpretation of the data from the Likert and multiple response questions.

Population and Sampling

This study was conducted at the University of Makati in the Higher School ng UMak (HSU) Department located along J.P Rizal Ext., West Rembo Makati City. The selection of the research locale was based on the fact that this school is the pioneer senior high school that produced the first and the largest batch of senior high school graduates in the Philippines (Rappler, 2014). It also has Academic and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Tracks that were essential in the conduct of the present study. There were 2 groups of respondents in the study - the student respondents and teacher respondents. The population of the student respondents was taken from the 2 main tracks which are the Academic Track and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track. The identified respondents from the 2 tracks were stratified according to strands wherein the Academic track consists of ABM, STM, and HSS strands while the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track has AUT, CPG, CSS, DFT, EIM, ELP, HRS, and TRM strands. The researcher identified a population of approximately 2248 Grade 11 students who were enrolled in the 2 tracks for the school

year 2019-2020. The sample size was 474 computed using Slovin's online sample size calculator with 95% confidence level and 4% margin of error. Through the application of stratified proportional sampling, the computed 474 sample size was proportionally taken from the 11 strata (strands) of the identified population; thus, the number of sample size per stratum consisted of 84 out of 403 ABM, 92 out of 439 STM, 116 out of 553 HSS, 9 out of 45 AUT, 18 out of 86 CPG, 19 out of 92 CSS, 10 out of 47 DFT, 8 out of 38 EIM, 16 out of 76 ELP, 58 out of 279 HRS, and 44 TRM out of 212 students. On the other hand, there were 20 research teachers identified as the total population for the teacher respondents; and through the use of the same sample size calculator, confidence level, and margin of error, still, the computed sample size for the teacher respondents was 20.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the Grade 11 students and Practical Research 1 teachers of the HSU Department, University of Makati, during the school year 2019-2020. Primarily, the researcher selected Grade 11 students as respondents because they are unacquainted with the concepts of research course, unlike Grade 12 students who experience research in Practical Research 1. Moreover, many of Grade 11 students experience troubles with their academic performances since their subjects, including research, are different compared to what in the junior high school (Atencio, 2021). Grade 11 students are still in the process of revising their former concrete thinking into fuller

understanding of principles as they transcend the basic knowledge in junior high school and try to decipher the complex concepts in senior high school (Manitoba Education & Training, 2020). Thus, they are more inclined with possible learning difficulties. The respondents were proportionally taken from diverse strands of 2 different tracks, namely: Academic Track and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track. There are 3 offered strands in Academic Track where some respondents were taken from, namely: ABM, HSS, and STM while the 8 strands, namely: AUT, CPG, CSS, DFT, EIM, ELP, HRS, and TRM are under Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track. All in all, there are 11 strands involved in the study which are ABM, STM, HSS, AUT, CPG, CSS, DFT, EIM, ELP, HRS, and TRM with varied sexes and socio-economic status. The respondents from different strands were selected and compared because they could have different perceptions on difficulty in acquiring the learning competencies of research. Based on the findings of Houtte & Stevens (2009), students from the non-academic track have negative attitude towards academic involvement while students from the academic track are more likely to cope with subject matters. As mentioned by Ajzen (1985), the negative attitude might be due to underlying factors such as lack of practice or knowledge in writing. Hence, Grade 11 students from varied strands were selected as the respondents of the study. Conversely, the teacher respondents who are expert and experienced in the field of teaching Practical Research 1 were purposively selected to provide specific data about the difficulties encountered by the

students. Teacher observation on the students learning difficulties has been accepted readily in the past as valid source of information for recording and reporting students' demonstration of the learning competencies (Maxwell, 2001). Thus, in this study, teachers' observation on the specific learning difficulties of students in the course served as evidence which accurately represented the difficulties. There were 20 teacher respondents of the study, and all had experienced teaching Practical Research 1 to Academic and Tec-Voc tracks. So, after the student respondents had identified the difficult learning competencies of Practical Research 1, the teacher respondents provided the specific aspects of difficulties encountered by students based on their first-hand experience in teaching the subject.

Research Instrument

Researcher-made survey questionnaire was utilized in this study. The instrument underwent preliminary survey participated by teachers in research as the respondents. This preliminary survey was used to identify the most challenging learning competencies in Practical Research 1 and to determine the learning competencies that were essentially included in the final survey questionnaires. There were 2 survey questionnaires used in the final data collection. The first survey questionnaire was for the student respondents which aimed to identify the difficult learning competencies of Practical Research 1. It was composed of 35 5-point Likert Scale questions which identified the difficult learning competencies encountered by students and 1 open-ended question or a free-written point

of view about the factors that contribute to the identified difficult learning competencies. On the other hand, the second survey questionnaire for the teacher respondents was given after the difficult learning competencies were already identified by the student respondents through the first survey. So, the second survey questionnaire was composed of 11 multiple response questions that aimed to gather specifications of the 14 difficult learning competencies identified by the student respondents in the first conducted survey. The survey questionnaires were written in Google Forms and the questions were based on the required learning competencies written on the Department of Education Practical Research 1 curriculum guide that includes understanding, preparing, conducting, writing, and presenting research while the open-ended question served as a supplemental question about the factors that contributed to their Likert Scale responses.

Validation of the Instrument

The primary survey questionnaire for student respondents underwent reliability test for its internal consistency through analysis of one data set from the pilot test of 50 respondents to ensure the stability of the instrument and to determine possible errors. The internal consistency of data set from the pilot test was 0.93 or in the range point of excellent internal consistency. The data were analyzed using Cronbach's alpha which is the most common measure to get the internal consistency. It is the commonly used measure when a study has multiple Likert questions in a questionnaire that forms a scale and a researcher

wishes to determine if the scale is reliable (Laerd Statistics, 2018). The use of pilot testing is according to the broadly accurate principle which requires testing the survey questionnaire on at least 30 to 100 pilot respondents before the full-scale administration of the instrument (SAGE, 2016); and if the same result is consistently achieved by using the same instrument under the same circumstances, the measurement is considered reliable (Laerd Statistics, 2018). The pilot testing was conducted online through Google Forms considering that no face-to-face classes were observed due to the pandemic. Thus, the researcher coordinated with the assigned class advisers for sending the online survey link to the target respondents. In addition, an expert-driven validation was employed to the 2 survey questionnaires used in the study to examine the appropriateness of their content. The researcher asked 3 field experts to examine the survey items by judging how well each item would reflect the concept that the study would intend to measure. The instrument was validated by the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) professors from De la Salle University-Dasmariñas, with the following credentials: a curriculum development professor who examined the relevance of the learning competencies included in the instrument; an Academic Writing professor who scrutinized the included learning competencies about academic literacy; and a research professor who counterchecked the inclusion of the survey items for the appropriate outcome. Soliciting such expert appraisals of every survey question can be an extremely valuable strategy for identifying problems and fine-tuning

items to collect optimal measurements (Jansen & Hak, 2005).

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection was undertaken a week after the students had completed the Practical Research 1 course. There were 2 phases of survey conducted in the study, namely: the primary survey for student respondents and the secondary survey for the teacher respondents. The primary survey aimed to gain data about the difficult learning competencies encountered by students in the course while the secondary survey aimed to provide specific aspects of difficulties encountered by students based on the first-hand experience of teachers in teaching the course. To begin with the undertaken procedures, the researcher sent a letter that contained the nature and purpose of the study to the Dean of the HSU Department at the University of Makati. The letter served as the formal request to ask for the participation of Grade 11 students and research teachers as respondents of the study and to coordinate with class advisers of Grade 11 students for the conduct of the final survey. The approved letter from the dean was sent to the research teachers and advisers as notice to ask for their assistance and coordination. After that, the researcher sent a copy of the relevant files which were the request letter signed by the dean, the consent of participation form, and the informed consent form to the teacher respondents and to the respective class advisers who forwarded it to the Grade 11 student respondents. The pilot test and full-scale online survey were conducted after the consent to participate, and the

informed consent form was filled out by the respondents and parents (for the minor respondents). The survey questionnaires used in the study contained multiple 35 Likert questions with a scale of 1- very difficult, 2-difficult, 3-neutral, 4-easy, and 5-very easy (Vagias, 2006) and 11 multiple response questions that were written on the Google forms. With the help of class advisers, the link of the survey questionnaire for the student respondents was directly sent to the president of the class who disseminated the link to the rest of his or her classmates while the link for the teacher respondents was directly sent by the researcher to each participating teacher. Finally, the researcher checked on the summary of the responses generated from Google Forms and the data gathered in the online survey were treated with utmost confidentiality following the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Analysis of Data

The numerical data were analyzed through descriptive statistics, T-Test, and one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The hypotheses of the study were set first with .05 (5%) level of significance. Then, the demographic profile of the student respondents, the difficult learning competencies identified by the student respondents, and the specific aspects of the difficult learning competencies determined by the teacher respondents were analyzed and presented through mean, frequency, and percentage. After the data on demographic profile and difficulties encountered by students had been determined, the significant difference between difficulties encountered by males and females was analyzed

through identifying the t-value of the two independent samples and was compared with the critical value which has an alpha level of .05(5%). The computed value from the T-test or the T-score decided to accept or reject the hypothesis on students' sex. Subsequently, the significant differences in the perception of the respondents in different socio-economic statuses and strands were compared through One-way ANOVA. The same process with the t-value, the computed value from the ANOVA or the F-score determined the acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis on socio-economic status and strands. The researcher consulted a statistician to ensure accurate computation and processing of numerical data in the study, including the hypothesis testing. Furthermore, all data were generated, computed, and analyzed using Excel. Hence, the statistical tools and software used in this study were appropriately chosen to easily generate and analyze data.

On the other hand, the textual data from the open-ended question in the survey questionnaire for the student respondents were categorized and converted into numerical data using quantitative content analysis. Quantitative content analysis is defined as a method of identifying patterns or themes and then counting their frequency (Luo, 2020). Thus, after the categorization of the textual data, the data were numerically coded and represented through frequency and percentage. The categorized data were validated through inter-coding and member checking to build their trustworthiness. In the early stage of categorizing data, the researcher asked help from 2 inter-coders who are research

teachers to comment and compare the consistency of the researcher's coding. After checking the consistency of coding, the member checking validation was employed wherein the coded data were returned to the respondents to check if the themes were accurate to their experiences. The converted numerical data from the quantitative content analysis were presented through frequency and percentage and were used as support to the interpretation of the results and hypothesis.

Statistical Treatment of Data

This study applied different statistical tools to treat the data. Descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, and percentage were used to present the demographic profile and encountered difficulties of the respondents. The researcher computed the following scoring range to categorize the level of difficulty in each item with the class width of 0.80 per interval: 1.00-1.79 (very difficult), 1.80-2.59 (difficult), 2.60-3.39 (neutral), 3.40-4.19 (easy), and 4.20-5.00 (very easy). In the hypothesis testing, T-Test was used to determine the significant difference in the encountered difficulties of the respondents according to their sex while one-way ANOVA was utilized to determine the significant difference in the encountered difficulties according to the respondents' socio-economic status and strand. Consequently, the interpretations of the result from the Likert and multiple response questions were supported by the results from the open-ended question in the primary survey.

Ethical Considerations

To assure that the study would follow ethical standards, the researcher declared a conflict of interest because of her affiliation to the institution where the study was conducted. However, it was resolved by choosing student respondents that were not from the handled classes of the researcher to avoid influence or control over the students' views and actions. Thus, the researcher asked for approval from the University of Makati and ensured an approved consent to participate from the respondents and their parents. The ethical standards of the study were reviewed and approved by the ethics review committee of De La Salle University-Dasmariñas before the actual conduct of the study.

Chapter 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Limitations of the Study

The findings on the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students and the factors that contribute to the difficulties were based on the professed experiences of student respondents and teacher respondents and not based on the students' actual performance (written output or grade) in the research course. Also, the findings do not represent the views of the all the Grade 11 students in the University of Makati but were only limited to views of students in Academic and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track.

Results

This quantitative study aims to identify the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 Students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. Initially, the data of the study were gathered from the online survey participated in by the Grade 11 students of Academic and TVL Tracks who took Practical Research 1 in the school year 2019-2020 and the Practical Research 1 teachers who have been teaching the course for years. The learning competencies included in the study are from the listed competencies of Practical Research 1 written in the curriculum guide of the DepEd while the difficulties are the particular aspects of the learning competencies that are found difficult to be performed or accomplished by the students.

Research Question No. 1. Demographic Profile of Grade 11 students as to sex, socio-economic status, and strand

Primarily, the demographic profiles of Grade 11 students were treated as factors that could have contributed to the difficulties they encountered in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. Consequently, the data about the students' sex, socio-economic status, and strand were collected. The frequency distribution of Grade 11 students according to sex is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Frequency Distribution of Grade 11 Students according to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male (1)	169	35.65%
Female (2)	305	64.35%
	n = 474	100%

As shown in Table 1, there are 474 respondents in the study composed of 169 males or 35.65% and 305 females or 64.35% of the total sample population. Thus, the number of female respondents is larger than the number of male respondents.

The socio-economic status of the respondents was treated as an independent variable, same as sex and strand, which could inflict differences on the difficulties encountered by students on learning competencies. Table 2 presents the frequency distribution of Grade 11 students according to socio-economic status.

Table 2

Frequency Distribution of Grade 11 Students according to Socio-Economic Status

Range of Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
Poor (Less than Php 9,520)	159	33.54%
Low Income but not Poor (Php 9,520 – Php 19,040)	171	36.08%
Lower Middle Class (Php 19,040 – Php 38,080)	89	18.78%
Middle Middle Class (Php 38,080 – Php 66,640)	25	5.27%
Upper Middle Class		

(Php 66,640 – Php 114,240)	22	4.64%
Upper Class but not Rich (Php 114,240 – Php 190,400)	5	1.05%
Rich (At least Php 190,400)	3	0.63%
n = 474		100%

Table 2 presents the socio-economic status of the respondents based on the monthly income range suggested in the Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES), 2017. As shown in the table, there are 474 respondents in the study, 159 of them or 33.54% are identified as Poor or have a monthly income of less than Php 9,520 while 171 respondents or 36.08% are identified as Low income but not poor or have monthly income ranging from Php 9,520 – Php 19,040. Also, 89 respondents or 18.78% of the are considered as Lower middle class or have a monthly income ranging from Php 19,040 – Php 38,080 and 25 respondents or 5.27% are considered as in the Middle middle class or have income ranging from Php 38,080 – Php 66,640. Furthermore, 22 respondents or 4.64% are in the Upper middle class or have income ranging from Php 66,640 – Php 114,240, then 5 respondents or 1.05% are in the Upper class but not rich which have income ranging from Php 114,240 – Php 190,400. And only 3 respondents or 0.63% are identified as Rich or have a monthly income of at least Php 190,400. Hence, most of the respondents belong to the Poor and Low income but not poor socio-economic classes.

The respondents of the study were from the Academic and TVL strands which may

have differences in terms of the difficulties encountered in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. Table 3 presents the frequency distribution of Grade 11 students according to strand.

Table 3

Frequency Distribution of Grade 11 Students according to Strand

Strand	Frequency	Percentage
ABM	84	17.72%
HUMSS	116	24.47%
STEM	92	19.41%
AUT	9	1.90%
CPG	18	3.80%
CSS	19	4.01%
DFT	10	2.11%
EIM	8	1.69%
ELP	16	3.38%
HRS	58	12.24%
TRM	44	9.28%
	n = 474	100%

As shown in Table 3, the sample size of the study consists of 474 respondents. The 474 respondents were proportionally taken from the different strands under Academic and TVL Tracks using stratified proportional sampling. The strands under the Academic track are ABM, HUMSS, and STEM; while the strands under TVL Track are AUT, CPG, CSS, DFT, EIM, ELP, HRS, and TRM. Thus, the number of respondent per strata consists of 84

or 17.72% ABM, 116 or 24.47% HSS, 92 or 19.41% STM, 9 or 1.90% AUT, 18 or 3.80 % CPG, 19 or 4.01% CSS, 10 or 2.11% DFT, 8 or 1.69 % EIM, 16 or 3.38 % ELP, 58 or 12.24 % HRS, and 44 or 9.28 % TRM students. HUMSS strand has the highest sample size since it has the largest population among the strands, so as with the lowest number of sample size from EIM for it has the smallest population among strands.

Research Question No. 2. Difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1 and the factors that Contribute to the difficulties

Practical Research 1 encompasses the learning competencies that are described as knowledge or skills that must be acquired by students in a particular course. Hence, students might encounter difficulties when dealing with the learning competencies. Table 4 presents the specific difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1.

Table 4

Difficulties Encountered by Grade 11 Students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1

Difficulty Mean	The Difficulties Encountered by Grade 11 Students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1	Frequency	Percentage
2.23	1. Oral presentation of the written research report		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using English language in the oral presentation (vocabulary, formality, & complexity) 18 90% • Answering questions from panel. 18 90% • Maintaining good non-verbal communication (eye contact, posture, & gesture) 4 20%
2.36	<p>2. Finalizing Research Output</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewing and revising the content (cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, & citations) 18 90% • Searching for proof-readers 13 65%
2.42	<p>3. Knowing the search process (Choose research topic, identify research problem, develop research questions, create research design, write proposal)</p> <p>Defining what a research problem is and describing the process of writing it 15 75%</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining what research design is and describing the process of developing it 13 65% • Defining what a research topic is and describing the process of writing it 9 45% • Defining what a research proposal is and describing the process of writing it 5 25%
2.43	<p>4. Selecting relevant literature</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Searching for relevant literature 16 80% • Finding free and credible sources 15 75% • Evaluating the significance of the theories or ideas from a literature to be included in the literature review 15 75%

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Skimming and scanning the research articles or any literature to be included in the literature review	7	35%
2.51	5. Writing coherent review of literature, 6. Presenting vast review, and 7. Synthesizing information from relevant literature		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Paraphrasing and summarizing the ideas from any literature to be integrated in the review of literature	18	90%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Combining the ideas and findings of the multiple sources in order to make an overall point	13	65%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Using transitional devices to connect ideas	9	45%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Identifying and addressing research gaps	9	45%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Maintaining the logical flow of the argument and ideas in the text	11	55%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Using correct citation and referencing format (APA, MLA, etc.)	11	55%
2.51	8. Relating the research findings with pertinent literature		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Writing logical discussion of research findings	16	80%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Searching pertinent literature related to the findings of the present study	11	55%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Connecting the findings of the present study to the relevant findings of foregoing studies	11	55%
2.52	9. Writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.)		
	10. Planning data collection and analysis procedures		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Evaluating other methods from different studies that could be used in the present study	13	65%

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Deciding the best research design, locale, population, data collection, and data analysis for the study	13	65%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Elaborating the research design	11	55%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Elaborating the data collection and data analysis	9	45%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Elaborating the research locale	5	25%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Elaborating the research population, sample size, and sampling technique	5	25%
2.53	11. Utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Utilizing research materials such as observation sheets, interview questionnaires, and survey questionnaires and employing qualitative data collection techniques such as observation, interview, focused group discussion, etc.	20	100%
2.57	12. Drawing conclusions from patterns and themes		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Analyzing themes to creating conclusion	13	65%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Integrating the generated themes in writing conclusion	13	65%
2.57	13. Describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc.)		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Reciting the characteristics of research	20	100%
2.58	14. Creating patterns and themes from data		

• Identifying the patterns in the coded data	13	65%
• Coding the data	11	55%
• Combining the codes to generate themes	11	55%
• Defining and naming themes	7	35%
• Reviewing the generated themes	5	25%
• Overviewing the data	4	20%

N=20

Table 4 presents the specific difficulties encountered by the Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research1. Primarily, the corresponding difficulty mean of each learning competency was from the average responses of the student respondents on the difficulty level of the 36 learning competencies in Practical Research 1 while the specific aspects of difficulty listed under each of the identified difficult learning competency were from the responses of the teacher respondents based on their first-hand experience in teaching the course. As shown in the Table 4, only 14 out of 36 learning competencies (scientific and language) were identified by the student respondents as difficult learning competencies and under each difficult learning competency were the particularized difficulties encountered by students which were identified by the 20 teacher respondents. The difficulty of each learning competency was measured through Likert Scale scoring range as follows: 1.00-1.79 (very difficult), 1.80-2.59 (difficult), 2.60-3.39 (neutral), 3.40-4.19 (easy), and 4.20-5.00 (very easy). The 14 identified difficult learning

competencies of Practical Research 1 are the following: 1) *oral presentation of the written research report*, 2) *Finalizing Research Output*, 3) *knowing the search process (choose research topic, identify research problem, develop research questions, create research design, write proposal)*, 4) *selecting relevant literature*, 5) *writing coherent review of literature*, 6) *presenting vast review*, 7) *synthesizing information from relevant literature*, 8) *relating the research findings with pertinent literature*, 9) *writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.)*, 10) *planning data collection and analysis procedures*, 11) *utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output*, 12) *drawing conclusions from patterns and themes*, 13) *describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc., and* 14) *creating patterns and themes from data*. Under the difficult learning competencies are the specific difficulties encountered by the students presented with frequency and percentage. Consequently, the competency that garnered the largest difficulty mean of 2.23 is *oral presentation of the written research report*. This involves the difficulty in using English language in the oral presentation (vocabulary, formality, & complexity.), maintaining good non-verbal communication (eye contact, posture, & gesture), and answering questions from panel. The 2nd difficult competency that has the difficulty mean of 2.49 is *finalizing research output*. This includes the difficulty in searching for proof-readers and reviewing and revising the content of the final paper

(cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, & citations). The 3rd s in difficult with a mean of 2.42 is *knowing the search process*. This includes the difficulty in defining and describing the research topic, research problem, research design, and research proposal. The 4th difficult competency that has the difficulty mean of 2.43 is *selecting relevant literature*. This involves the difficulty in searching for relevant literature, finding free and credible sources, skimming and scanning the research articles or any literature to be included in the literature review, and evaluating the significance of the theories or ideas from a literature to be included in the literature review. The 5th-7th difficult competencies in the list are the 3 related competencies about writing literature review that are combined and emerged with one difficulty mean of 2.51. The 3 combined competencies are *writing coherent review of literature, presenting vast review, and synthesizing information from relevant literature* which involve the difficulty in using correct citation and referencing format (APA, MLA, etc.), paraphrasing and summarizing the ideas from any literature to be integrated in the review of literature, using transitional devices to connect ideas, maintaining the logical flow of the argument and ideas in the text, identifying and addressing research gaps, and combining the ideas and findings of the multiple sources in order to make an overall point. The 8th difficult competency with a mean of 2.51, equal with the difficulty mean of the 5th-7th competencies, is *relating the research findings with pertinent literature*. This includes difficulty of searching pertinent literature related to the

findings of the present study, connecting the findings of the present study to the relevant findings of foregoing studies, and writing a logical discussion of research findings. Furthermore, the 9th -10th in the list are the 2 related competencies combined and emerged with the difficulty mean of 2.52. The 2 combined competencies are *writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.) and planning data collection and analysis procedures*. These involve the difficulty in evaluating other methods from different studies and deciding and elaborating the best research design, locale, population, data collection, and data analysis of the study. The 11th difficult competency which has a mean of 2.53 is *utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output*, which involves difficulty in utilizing research materials such as observation sheets, interview questionnaires, and survey questionnaires; and difficulty of employing qualitative data collection techniques such as observation, interview, focused group discussion, etc. The 12th difficult competency that has a mean of 2.57 is *drawing conclusions from patterns and themes* which involves the difficulty of analyzing themes to create conclusion and integrating the generated themes in writing conclusion. The 13th difficult competency which has a mean of 2.57, equal to the difficulty mean of the 12th competency, is *describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc.)*. This comprises difficulty in reciting the characteristics of research. The 14th difficult competency that has a mean of 2.58 is *creating patterns and*

themes from data. This includes the difficulty in overviewing the data, coding the data, identifying the patterns in the coded data, combining the codes to generate themes, reviewing the generated themes, and defining and naming themes.

Similar to the previous table, Table 5 presents the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1, however, when grouped according to sex.

Table 5

Difficulties Encountered by Grade 11 Students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1 according to Sex

The Difficulties Encountered by Grade 11 Students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1	Difficulty Mean	
	Male	Female
1. Oral presentation of the written research report	2.27	2.21
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using English language in the oral presentation (vocabulary, formality, & complexity.) • Answering questions from panel • Maintaining good non-verbal communication (eye contact, posture, & gesture) 		
2. Finalizing Research Output	2.38	2.34
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewing and revising the content (cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, & citations) • Searching for proof-readers 		

3. Knowing the search process (Choose research topic, identify research problem, develop research questions, create research design, write proposal)

2.38

2.43

- Defining what a research problem is and describing the process of writing it
- Defining what research design is and describing the process of developing it
- Defining what a research topic is and describing the process of writing it
- Defining what a research proposal is and describing the process of writing it

4. Selecting relevant literature

2.43

2.43

- Searching for relevant literature
- Finding free and credible sources
- Evaluating the significance of the theories or ideas from a literature to be included in the literature review
- Skimming and scanning the research articles or any literature to be included in the literature review

5. Writing coherent review of literature, 6. Presenting vast review, and 7. Synthesizing information from relevant literature

2.52

2.50

- Paraphrasing and summarizing the ideas from any literature to be integrated in the review of literature.
- Combining the ideas and findings of the multiple sources in order to make an overall point
- Using transitional devices to connect ideas
- Identifying and addressing research gaps
- Maintaining the logical flow of the argument and ideas in the text
- Using correct citation and referencing format (APA, MLA, etc.)

8. Relating the research findings with pertinent literature

2.55

2.49

- Writing a logical discussion of research findings
- Searching pertinent literature related to the findings of the present study

- Connecting the findings of the present study to the relevant findings of foregoing studies

9. Writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.)

10. Planning data collection and analysis procedures

2.53 2.51

- Evaluating other methods from different studies that could be used in the present study
- Deciding the best research design, locale, population, data collection, and data analysis for the study
- Elaborating the research design
- Elaborating the data collection and data analysis.
- Elaborating the research locale
- Elaborating the research population, sample size, and sampling technique

11. Utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output

2.6 2.49

- Utilizing research materials such as observation sheets, interview questionnaires, and survey questionnaires and employing qualitative data collection techniques such as observation, interview, focused group discussion, etc.

12. Drawing conclusions from patterns and themes

2.54 2.58

- Analyzing themes to create conclusion
- Integrating the generated themes in writing conclusion

13. Describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc.)

2.38 2.67

- Reciting the characteristics of research

14. Creating patterns and themes from data

2.56 2.6

- Identifying the patterns in the coded data.

- Coding the data
- Combining the codes to generate themes
- Defining and naming themes
- Reviewing the generated themes
- Overviewing the data

Overall Mean =

2.47

2.48

■ Difficult ■ Neutral

Table 5 presents the computed difficulty mean of the each of the 14 difficult learning competencies identified in the study and the specific aspects of the difficulty according to sex. Specifically, it presents the difficulty encountered by male and female respondents towards each learning competency. The difficulty mean according to sex was determined by the Likert Scale scoring range as follows: 1.00-1.79 (very difficult), 1.80-2.59 (difficult), 2.60-3.39 (neutral), 3.40-4.19 (easy), and 4.20-5.00 (very easy). As seen in the table, both males and females encountered difficulty in learning competency numbers 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, and 12. Conversely, the data suggest that only male respondents encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 13 and 14 while it seems that only the female respondents encountered difficulty in the learning competency number 11. Although both sexes encountered difficulties in most of the listed competencies; conversely, male respondents displayed difficulties in reciting the characteristics of research and in creating patterns and themes in qualitative data analysis while female respondents displayed difficulties in the utilization of materials to produce research output.

Moreover, Table 6 presents the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 but specific on socio-economic status.

Table 6

Difficulties Encountered by Grade 11 Students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1 according to Socio-economic Status

Difficulties Encountered by Grade 11 Students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1	Difficulty Mean						
	Less than Php 9,520	Php 9,520 to 19,040	Php 19,040 to 38,080	Php 38,080 to 66,640	Php 66,640 to 114,240	Php 114,240 to 190,400	At least Php 190,400
1. Oral presentation of the written research report	2.27	2.14	2.34	2.12	2.27	2.8	1.67
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using English language in the oral presentation (vocabulary, formality, & complexity.) Answering questions from panel 							

- Maintaining good non-verbal communication (eye contact, posture, & gesture)

2. Finalizing Research Output 2.39 2.25 2.51 2.52 2.14 2.2 2.67

- Reviewing and revising the content (cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, & citations)

- Searching for proof-readers

3. Knowing the search process (Choose research topic, identify research problem, develop research questions, create research design, write proposal)

- Defining what a research problem is and describing the process of writing it
- Defining what research design is and describing the process of developing it
- Defining what a research topic is and describing the process of writing it

2.38 2.4 2.44 2.44 2.59 3 2

- Defining what a research proposal is and describing the process of writing it

4. Selecting relevant literature

2.44 2.47 2.4 2.32 2.27 2.6 2.33

- Searching for relevant literature.
- Finding free and credible sources
- Evaluating the significance of the theories or ideas from a literature to be included in the literature review
- Skimming and scanning the research articles or any literature to be included in the literature review

5. Writing coherent review of literature, 6. Presenting vast review, and 7. Synthesizing information from relevant literature

2.53 2.49 2.54 2.45 2.4 2.27 2.27

- Paraphrasing and summarizing the ideas from any literature to be integrated in the review of literature.
- Combining the ideas and findings of the multiple sources in order to make an overall point

- Using transitional devices to connect ideas
- Identifying and addressing research gaps
- Maintaining the logical flow of the argument and ideas in the text
- Using correct citation and referencing format (APA, MLA, etc.)

8. Relating the research findings with pertinent literature

2.57 2.48 2.59 2.28 2.45 2.2 2

- Writing a logical discussion of research findings
- Searching pertinent literature related to the findings of the present study
- Connecting the findings of the present study to the relevant findings of foregoing studies

9. Writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.); 10. Planning data collection and

2.54 2.5 2.55 2.54 2.36 3 2

**analysis
procedures**

- Evaluating other methods from different studies that could be used in the present study
- Deciding the best research design, locale, population, data collection, and data analysis for the study
- Elaborating the research design
- Elaborating the data collection and data analysis
- Elaborating the research locale
- Elaborating the research population, sample size, and sampling technique

11. Utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output

- Utilizing research materials such as observation sheets, interview questionnaires, and survey questionnaires and employing qualitative data

2.61 2.51 2.47 2.4 2.32 3.4 1.67

collection techniques such as observation, interview, focused group discussion, etc.

12. Drawing conclusions from patterns and themes 2.54 2.6 2.67 2.4 2.18 2.6 2.33

- Analyzing themes to create conclusion
- Integrating the generated themes in writing conclusion

13. Describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc.) 2.4 2.66 2.71 2.64 2.41 2.6 3.67

- Reciting the characteristics of research

14. Creating patterns and themes from data 2.55 2.57 2.7 2.44 2.5 3.2 2.67

- Identifying the patterns in the coded data
- Coding the data
- Combining the codes to generate themes
- Defining and naming themes
- Reviewing the generated themes
- Overviewing the data

Overall Mean = 2.47 2.46 2.54 2.41 2.35 2.72 2.47

■ Difficult ■ Neutral

Table 6 presents the computed difficulty mean of each of the competencies and the specific difficulties (scientific and language) encountered the students in the 14 out of 36 learning competencies of Practical Research 1 according to their socio-economic status. The difficulty mean of each competency is categorized according to the socio-economic status of students and is determined by the Likert Scale scoring range as follows: 1.00-1.79 (very difficult), 1.80-2.59 (difficult), 2.60-3.39 (neutral), 3.40-4.19 (easy), and 4.20-5.00 (very easy). Accordingly, each group is classified according to its monthly income (See socio-economic classification in Table 2). As shown in the table, the difficulties encountered by the different groups vary differently according to their socio-economic status. The learning competencies that are identified as difficult per socio-economic group are listed in the following sequence: 1) Php 9,520 per month or the ‘Poor’ encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 , 12, 13, and 14; 2) Php 9,520 to Php19, 040 per month or the ‘Low income but not poor’ encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 ,11, and 14; 3) Php 19,040 to Php 38,080 per month or the ‘Lower Middle Class’ encountered difficulties in the learning competencies number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 ,11, and 14; 4) Php 38,080 to Php 66,640 per month or the ‘Middle Middle Class’ encountered difficulties in the

learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 ,11, 12, and 14; 5) Php 66,640 to Php 109,200 per month or the ‘Upper Middle Class’ encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 ,11, 12, 13, and 14 ; 6) Php 114,240 to Php 190,400 per month or the ‘Upper income but not rich’ encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 14; 7) at least PHP 190,400 per month or the ‘Rich’ encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 ,11, and 12. All the socio-economic groups similarly display difficulty in the overall difficulty mean except the group of Php 114,240 to Php 190,400 per month or the ‘Upper income but not rich’ which displays neutrality in the overall difficulty mean.

Table 7 is the last table to present the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 but this time when grouped according to strand.

Table 7

Difficulties Encountered by Grade 11 Students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1 according to Strand

The Difficulties Encountered by Grade 11 Students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1	Difficulty Mean											
	ABM	HSS	STM	AUT	CPG	CSS	DFT	EIM	ELP	HRS	TRM	
1. Oral presentation of the written	2.15	2.19	2.17	2	2.06	2.42	2.6	2.63	2.44	2.34	2.27	

research report.

- Using English language in the oral presentation (vocabulary, formality, & complexity.)
- Answering questions from panel
- Maintaining good non-verbal communication (eye contact, posture, & gesture)

2. Finalizing

Research Output.

- Reviewing and revising the content (cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, & citations)
- Searching for proof-readers.

3. Knowing the search process (Choose research topic, identify research problem, develop research question, create research design, write proposal)

- Defining what a research problem is and describing the process of writing it

2.26 2.27 2.51 1.78 2.4 2.47 2.8 2.75 2.38 2.36 2.3

2.39 2.39 2.58 1.67 2.5 2.16 2.6 2.75 2.44 2.29 2.5

- Defining what research design is and describing the process of developing it
- Defining what a research topic is and describing the process of writing it
- Defining what a research proposal is and describing the process of writing it

4. Selecting

relevant literature

2.36 2.51 2.51 2 2.28 2.53 2.4 2.87 2.38 2.4 2.27

- Searching for relevant literature
- Finding free and credible sources
- Evaluating the significance of the theories or ideas from a literature to be included in the literature review
- Skimming and scanning the research articles or any literature to be included in the literature review

5. Writing

coherent review of literature, 6.

Presenting vast review, and 7.

2.45 2.53 2.56 2.22 2.69 2.55 2.6 2.8 2.61 2.43 2.38

Synthesizing information from relevant literature.

- Paraphrasing and summarizing the ideas from any literature to be integrated in the review of literature
 - Combining the ideas and findings of the multiple sources in order to make an overall point
 - Using transitional devices to connect ideas.
 - Identifying and addressing research gaps
 - Maintaining the logical flow of the argument and ideas in the text
 - Using correct citation and referencing format (APA, MLA, etc.)
- 8. Relating the research findings with pertinent literature**
- Writing a logical discussion of research findings
 - Searching pertinent literature related to the findings of the present study

2.4 2.62 2.59 2.3 2.78 2.53 2.6 2.75 2.81 2.29 2.34

- Connecting the findings of the present study to the relevant findings of foregoing studies

9. Writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.); 10. Planning data collection and analysis procedures

- Evaluating other methods from different studies that could be used in the present study
- Deciding the best research design, locale, population, data collection, and data analysis for the study
- Elaborating the research design
- Elaborating the data collection and data analysis
- Elaborating the research locale
- Elaborating the research population, sample size, and sampling technique

2.55 2.45 2.62 2.15 2.59 2.45 2.75 2.88 2.55 2.45 2.62

11. Utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output

2.51 2.54 2.66 2.4 2.4 2.37 2.8 3 2.56 2.36 2.41

- Utilizing research materials such as observation sheets, interview questionnaires, and survey questionnaires and employing qualitative data collection techniques such as observation, interview, focus group discussion, etc.

12. Drawing conclusions from patterns and themes

2.55 2.58 2.76 2.2 2.56 2.47 2.7 2.63 2.81 2.41 2.34

- Analyzing themes to create conclusion.
- Integrating the generated themes in writing conclusion

13. Describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc.)

2.57 2.55 2.7 2 2.61 2.53 2.7 2.5 2.69 2.55 2.39

- Reciting the characteristics of research

14. Creating patterns and themes from data

2.64 2.52 2.66 2.56 2.67 2.47 2.8 2.5 2.75 2.45 2.59

- Identifying the patterns in the coded data
- Coding the data.
- Combining the codes to generate themes
- Defining and naming themes
- Reviewing the generated themes
- Overviewing the data

Overall Mean = 2.44 2.47 2.57 2.12 2.5 2.45 2.67 2.73 2.58 2.39 2.4

■ Very Difficult ■ Difficult ■ Neutral

As presented in Table 7, the difficulties encountered by different strands in the learning 14 out 36 learning competencies of Practical Research 1 are quite diverse. The difficulty mean was determined through the Likert Scale scoring range in the following sequence: 1.00-1.79 (very difficult), 1.80-2.59 (difficult), 2.60-3.39 (neutral), 3.40-4.19 (easy), and 4.20-5.00 (very easy). The above table presents the difficult learning competencies of Practical Research 1 and the specific aspects of difficulties (scientific and language) encountered by students according to strands elaborated in the following : 1) ABM encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, and 13 with an overall difficulty mean of 2.44; 2) HSS encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14 with an

overall difficulty mean of 2.47; 3) STM encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 with an overall difficulty mean of 2.57; 4) AUT encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14 ; however, learning competency number 2 was identified as very difficult in this strand with an overall difficulty mean of 2.12 which is the largest difficulty mean among all strands; 5) CPG encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 9, 10, 11, and 12 with an overall difficulty mean of 2.5; 6) CSS encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14 with an overall difficulty mean of 2.45; 7) DFT encountered difficulties in the learning competency 3 and 4 and displayed neutrality with the overall mean of 2.67; 8) EIM encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 13 and 14 and displayed neutrality with the overall mean of 2.73; 9) ELP encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 9, 10, and 11 with an overall difficulty mean of 2.58; 10) HRS encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14 with an overall difficulty mean of 2.39; and 11) TRM encountered difficulties in the learning competency number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 13, and 14 with an overall difficulty mean of 2.4. Subsequently, based on the data, 9 strands displayed difficulty in the overall mean of the 14 identified difficult learning competencies. These strands are ABM, HSS, STM, CPG, CSS, ELP, HRS, and TRM while 2 strands displayed neutrality in the overall mean

which are the DFT and EIM. Furthermore, AUT, HRS, and TRM have the largest difficulty mean among all strands. The mean score of AUT is 2.12, HRS is 2.39, and TRM is 2.4. This suggests that the 3 strands from the TVL Track displayed difficulty larger than the other strands.

The difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 which were mentioned in the preceding tables may be driven by some factors. Thus, Table 8 presents the factors that contributed to the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1

Table 8

Factors that Contributed to the Difficulties Encountered by Grade 11 Students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1

Factors that Contributed to the Difficulties	Frequency	Percentage
1. Teaching Instructions		
Insufficient discussion and explanation of research topics: no reiteration of technical terms and step-by-step research process	167	42.5%
2. Complexity of Research Parts		
Creating or writing Research title, Review of Related Literature, Statement of the Problem, and Data Analysis	76	19.34%
3. Time Constraint		
Limited time in learning and writing	45	11.45%

research

4. Insufficient Resources

Limited references (research journals, books, etc.), internet connection, computer, and printer	41	10.43%
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5. Language Skills

Difficulty in using English language in the written and oral presentation of research output	27	6.87%
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6. Lack of Cooperation from Group Members

Most group members are dependent to leader and to some active members	21	5.34%
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7. Data Gathering

Respondents are not willing to cooperate	16	4.07%
	n=393	100%

Table 8 presents the factors that contributed to the difficulties encountered by the students in the 14 out of 36 learning competencies of Practical Research 1. These factors are from the highlighted themes in the open-ended survey question responses. Accordingly, there are only 393 relevant responses that are recorded and categorized to form themes. Thus, as shown in the table, the 1st and highest factor that contributed to the difficulties encountered by students is “Teaching Instructions”, which consists of 167 or 42.5% of the total responses. The instructions used in teaching research are described as having insufficient discussion and explanation of research topics and lack reiteration of technical

terms and step-by-step research process. The 2nd factor that contributed to the difficulties encountered by students is “Complexity of Research Parts”, which consists of 76 or 19.34 % of the total responses, specifically, difficulties in constructing research title, review of related literature, statement of the problem, and data analysis. The 3rd factor is "Time Constraint", which consists of 45 or 11.45% of the total responses and is described as experiencing limited time in learning and writing research. In the 4th factor which is "Insufficient Resources", there are 41 or 10.43% responses that highlight limited references (research journals, books, etc.), internet connection, computer, and printer. The 5th identified factor is "Language Skills", which consists of 27 or 6.87% total responses and considered as the difficulty of using the English language in the written and oral presentation of research output. The 6th factor is about "Lack of Cooperation from Group Members", which has a total of 21 or 5.24% responses and described as where most group members are dependent on the leader and to some active members. Lastly, the 6th factor that contributed to the difficulties encountered by students is "Data Gathering", which consists of 16 or 4.07% of the total responses and is mainly about the difficulty of finding and persuading respondents to be part of the study. Among all factors, "Teaching Instructions" has the largest number of occurrences while the "Data Gathering" has the least number of occurrences.

Research Question No. 3. Significant difference on the encountered difficulties of

Grade 11 students in the Learning Competencies of Practical Research 1 when grouped according to sex, socio-economic status, and strand

This study was undertaken to determine the significant difference between the compared variables to accept or reject the hypothesis of the study. Particularly, Table 9 presents the T-test result on the significant difference between male’s and female’s encountered difficulties in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1.

Table 9

Test Statistics and Result (Sex)

	Test Statistic	P-value	Statistical Decision
T-score	-0.2	0.841	Failed to reject Ho

As seen in Table 9, the result of the T-test reveals no significant difference in the mean score between male and female respondents based on the computed P-value of 0.841 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05; thus, the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the encountered difficulties of male and female respondents in the 14 out of 36 learning competencies of Practical Research 1 has no significant difference or none between the 2 groups displaying a significantly larger difficulty level. Though the data in Table 5 presents the differences in the difficulties encountered by male and female students per learning competency; nevertheless, there is no significant difference calculated in the

overall difficulty mean of male which is 2.47 and female which is 2.48. Both groups show difficulty in dealing with the 14 identified difficult learning competencies of Practical Research 1.

Correspondingly, Table 10 presents the hypothesis test result through ANOVA on the significant difference of the difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 when grouped according to socio-economic status.

Table 10

Test Statistics and Result (SES)

	Test Statistic	P-value	Statistical Decision
F-score	1.523	0.151	Failed to reject Ho

As presented in Table 10, there is no significant difference in the difficulties encountered by the students as to their socio-economic status. The significant difference is determined by the F- core of 1.523 and the P-value of 0.151 which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Almost all the students who are grouped according to socio-economic status display difficulty in the listed competencies. Though there is one group that manifests neutrality which is the upper income but not rich; however, it has no great significance as reflected on the p-value. Besides, 6 out of 7 groups display difficulty based on the data in Table 6. Thus, there is no significant difference in the difficulties encountered

by students among different socio-economic classes as manifested by the data.

Lastly, Table 11 presents the hypothesis test result through ANOVA on the significant difference of the difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 when grouped according to strand.

Table 11

Test Statistics and Result (Strand)

	Test Statistic	P-value	Statistical Decision
F-score	2.388	0.013	Reject Ho

As shown in Table 11, the ANOVA test produced F-score of 2.388 and P-value of 0.013, which rejects the null hypothesis since the P-value is less than 0.05 significance level. Hence, there is a significant difference in the difficulties encountered by the students in different strands, considering that some of the strands have a larger difficulty mean compared to other strands. Based on the data from Table 7, the significant differences in the difficulties encountered by the various strands are shown on their total mean score garnered from the difficulty level of all 14 difficult learning competencies and are arranged from the largest to smallest difficulty level order: (1.) AUT- 2.12/Difficult, (2.) HRS- 2.39/Difficult, (3.) TRM- 2.4/ Difficult, (4.) ABM- 2.44/ Difficult, (5.) CSS -2.45/ Difficult,

(6.) HSS-2.47/ Difficult, (7.) CPG- 2.5/ Difficult, (8.)STM- 2.57/ Difficult, (9.) ELP - 2.58/ Difficult, (10.) DFT-2.67/ Neutral, and (11.) EIM-2.73/Neutral. There are 9 strands which show difficulty in the listed competencies. These are AUT, HRS, TRM, ABM, CSS, HSS, CPG, STM, and ELP while there are 2 strands, namely: DFT and EIM which display neutrality. Subsequently, the difficulty encountered by the different strands has significant difference and it seems that AUT, HRS, and TRM are the 3 strands that have larger difficulty when dealing with the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 than the other strands.

Discussion

The data administered through descriptive statistics and quantitative content analysis established the 3 major findings of the study which are 1) grade 11 students encountered difficulties in the learning competencies of Practical Research1. Specifically, they encountered difficulties (scientific and language) in the 14 out of 36 learning competencies. These difficulties are particularized in the following list: 1) *oral presentation of the written research report*. This involves the difficulty in using English language in the oral presentation (vocabulary, formality, & complexity.), maintaining good non-verbal communication (eye contact, posture, & gesture), and answering questions from panel, 2) *finalizing research output*. This includes the difficulty in searching for proof-readers and the difficulty in reviewing and revising the content of the final paper (cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, & citations), 3) *knowing the search process (choose*

research topic, identify research problem, develop research questions, create research design, write proposal. This includes the difficulty in defining and describing the research topic, research problem, research design, and research proposal, 4) *selecting relevant literature.* This involves the difficulty in searching for relevant literature, finding free and credible sources, skimming and scanning literature, and evaluating the significance of the theories or ideas from a literature to be included in the review, 5) *writing coherent review of literature,* 6) *presenting vast review,* 7) *synthesizing information from relevant literature.* The three competencies involve the difficulty in using correct citation and referencing format (APA, MLA, etc.), paraphrasing and summarizing the ideas from any literature to be integrated in the review of literature, using transitional devices to connect ideas, maintaining the logical flow of the argument and ideas in the text, identifying and addressing research gaps, and combining the ideas and findings of multiple sources in order to make an overall point. 8) *relating the research findings with pertinent literature.* This includes the difficulty of searching pertinent literature related to the findings of the present study, connecting the findings of the present study to the relevant findings of foregoing studies, and writing a logical discussion of research findings, 9) *writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.),* 10) *planning data collection and analysis procedures.* The two competencies include the difficulty in evaluating other methods from different studies and the difficulty in

deciding and elaborating the best research design, locale, population, data collection, and data analysis of the study, 11) *utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output*. This involves the difficulty in utilizing research materials such as observation sheets, interview questionnaires, and survey questionnaires; and the difficulty of employing qualitative data collection techniques such as observation, interview, focus group discussion, etc., 12) *drawing conclusions from patterns and themes*. This includes the difficulty of analyzing themes to create conclusion and integrating the generated themes in writing conclusion. 13) *describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc.)*. This includes the difficulty in reciting the characteristics of research, and 14) *creating patterns and themes from data*. This includes the difficulty in overviewing the data, coding the data, identifying the patterns in the coded data, combining the codes to generate themes, reviewing the generated themes, and defining and naming themes. The difficulties encountered by students might be associated with factors identified in the study which are: *teaching instructions, the complexity of research parts, time constraint, insufficient resources, language skills, lack of cooperation from group members, and data gathering*. The difficulties appeared to be significantly different between strands. Difficulty was manifested by the students in AUT, HRS, TRM, ABM, CSS, HSS, CPG, STM, and ELP. However, among the 9 strands that displayed difficulty, the students from AUT, HRS, and TRM strands had the largest difficulty mean.

Based on the 1st major findings, students encountered difficulties in the following learning competencies: 1) *oral presentation of the written research report*, 2) *finalizing research output*, 3) *knowing the search process (choose research topic, identify research problem, develop research questions, create research design, write proposal)*, 4) *selecting relevant literature*, 5) *writing coherent review of literature*, 6) *presenting vast review*, 7) *synthesizing information from relevant literature*, 8) *relating the research findings with pertinent literature*, 9) *writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.)*, 10) *planning data collection and analysis procedures*, 11) *utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output*, 12) *drawing conclusions from patterns and themes*, 13) *describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc.)*, and 14) *creating patterns and themes from data*. In the 14 learning competencies, the 1st is *oral presentation of the written research report* which has the largest difficulty mean of 2.23. It includes the difficulty encountered by students in using English in the oral presentation (vocabulary, formality, & complexity), maintaining good non-verbal communication (eye contact, posture, & gesture), and answering questions from panel. This suggests that students have difficulty in using verbal communication (especially in using English language in the oral presentation) and non-verbal communication and in answering the panel's questions. There might be factors that contributed to the difficulty encountered by the students in oral presentation. This is

substantiated by the previous findings of Chandran et al. (2015) which concluded that students may have initial anxiety in oral presentation due to some factors such as insufficient preparation, fear of making mistakes, fear of the audience, lack of confidence, and lack of confidence in language skills. Also, the difficulty in using English language in an oral presentation might be associated with the poor language skills such as vocabulary deficiency and difficulty in reading (Mclean et al., 2013). Furthermore, the present study also found that students have difficulty in maintaining non-verbal communication during the oral presentation such as eye contact, proper posture, and gestures. Non-verbal communication is important because it could help build rapport in oral presentation. According to the National Social Anxiety Center (2016), public speaking anxiety hinders proper non-verbal communication because the speaker might be incited by the fear of speaking in front of the audience. Also, if a presenter has difficulty in maintaining good non-verbal communication, it may indicate lack of confidence, control, or power over the presentation (Liam, 2019). Consequently, students who encountered difficulty in the non-verbal communication might have experienced anxiety in public speaking. The 2nd learning competency where students encountered difficulties is *finalizing research output*. This includes the difficulties in searching for proof-readers and reviewing and revising the content of the final paper (cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, & citations). The difficulty in searching in proof readers is primarily related to the availability and

affordability of the qualified proof readers, which is not associated to the individual capabilities of students. In the study of Roxas (2020), the students claimed that even after the revision of the final output, there were still errors that were not corrected and revised, thus feedback and guidance from qualified people was needed. However, the difficulty of reviewing and revising the content of the final paper (cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, & citations) could also be associated to the language skills of students since it requires knowledge in cohesion, grammar, punctuations, spelling, etc. Similar to the findings of Pablo et al. (2018), he found out that Grade 11 students had difficulties in writing academic essays and had poor to fair writing skills specifically in maintaining logical organization, good grammar, formality, and vocabulary. Moreover, the findings of Sumardi (2019) also identified that Grade 11 students had difficulty in choosing appropriate words to use in writing, spelling, and vocabulary. Hence, in the present findings, the difficulty experienced by students in reviewing and revising the content of the final paper (cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, & citations) could have been greatly affected by their writing skills or their ability to write with proper cohesion, grammar, punctuation, spelling, and citation. The 3rd learning competency is *knowing the search process*. This includes the difficulty encountered by students in defining and describing the research topic, research problem, research design, and research proposal. Since this is in the planning phase of research writing, it might be difficult to the students who are new to

research and have limited knowledge on research terminologies and processes of research to profoundly understand and define the research process. This is comparable to the findings of Muhammad (2019) in his study about problems encountered by students in writing the first research paper. Muhammad (2019) found that students had lack of familiarity with the format and process of research, which triggered the difficulty encountered by students in research writing. The 4th learning competency is *selecting relevant literature* which involves the difficulty in searching for relevant literature, finding free and credible sources, skimming and scanning the research articles or any literature, and evaluating the significance of the theories or ideas from a literature to be included in the literature review. In the 4th difficult competency, most of the encountered difficulties are about finding relevant, credible, and free sources which could be related to the problem of accessibility of the needed materials, given the fact that most of the credible journals necessitate payment to enable access. On the other hand, skimming, scanning, and critical reading of the text are part of the difficulty encountered by students in selecting relevant literature. Mainly, skimming and scanning techniques are two simple reading techniques which positively help students' reading comprehension (Setiawan, 2019), so these techniques could be useful when choosing relevant literature to be included in the study but may be overwhelming if done in numerous readings. Conversely, evaluative or critical reading is a more intense reading which involves critically evaluating and synthesizing

what is read. This technique is greatly useful in selecting relevant literature for a study, but the findings of Georgiou (2015) revealed that some students had poor critical reading skills. Nevertheless, a study found out that the use of scaffolding strategies such as modeling is effective for developing the critical reading of students (Salem, 2017). So, students who encounter difficulty in the reading techniques used in selecting relevant literature could be supported with scaffolding reading strategies. The 5th -7th competencies are 3 related competencies about writing literature review which are combined to emerge with a particular difficulty mean. The 3 combined competencies are *writing coherent review of literature, presenting vast review, and synthesizing information from relevant literature* which involve the difficulty of using correct citation and referencing format (APA, MLA, etc.), paraphrasing and summarizing the ideas from any literature to be integrated in the review of literature, using transitional devices to connect ideas, maintaining the logical flow of the argument and ideas in the text, identifying and addressing research gaps, and combining the ideas and findings of the multiple sources in order to make an overall point. The present findings may show the inadequacy of students' academic writing skills parallel to the findings of the earlier studies which concluded that some students find it difficult to write related literature because of their underdeveloped ability to cite, paraphrase, and summarize (Bloch, 2012; Campbell, 1990) and to maintain the logical organization of the text (Pablo et al. (2018). Language may also be a factor for this difficulty. In the study of

Roxas (2020), most of his senior high school respondents initially wrote their thoughts in Filipino before translating them to English, so it seems that there is a clear language barrier between students and their literature review writing task. Additionally, identifying and addressing research gap is one of the difficulties encountered by students in writing review of related literature. Identifying and addressing the gap is actually a difficult task because the researcher needs to consider the practical and theoretical implications of the proposed study either it could improve existing practice or build theoretical frameworks (North Central University, 2021). Hence writing the research gap requires critical evaluation and good decision making. The 8th competency where students encountered difficulties is *relating the research findings with pertinent literature*. This includes the difficulty of searching pertinent literature related to the findings of the present study, connecting the findings of the present study to the relevant findings of foregoing studies, and writing a logical discussion of research findings. Clearly, the difficulties encountered by students in the 8th competency focused on the ability to connect the present findings to the findings of the foregoing studies. This act may require sufficient reading comprehension and writing skills to understand the major findings of a related article and to effectively connect it to the present findings. Reading and writing are two interrelated skills (Burgess, 2021), so the students should comprehend the findings of related articles before integrating or writing them to their conclusion. Furthermore, the 9th -10th competencies are 2 related

competencies about research methodology combined to emerge with one difficulty mean. The 2 combined competencies are *writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.)*; and *planning data collection and analysis procedures*. These involve the difficulty in evaluating other methods from different studies and deciding and elaborating the best research design, locale, population, data collection, and data analysis of the study. The difficulties might could have emerged due to the students' limited knowledge in the research methodology and due to the serious planning and deciding of the most appropriate and convenient research design, respondents, and locale. For novice researchers, writing the methodology of a research paper can be an overwhelming process, especially considering the complex elements covered by this research section (Ellis & Levy, 2009). The 11th competency is *utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output* which involves the difficulty in utilizing research materials such as observation sheets, interview questionnaires, and survey questionnaires; and the difficulty of employing qualitative data collection techniques such as observation, interview, focus group discussion, etc. The findings suggest that the students experience difficulties in using the research materials and techniques in the data collection. It may be due to the difficult procedure of using materials and data collection process itself like the demanding processes of conducting a survey or interview. In the of Dearnley (as cited in Remando et al., 2015), student researchers encountered challenges in

conducting data collection in the process of choosing, locating, and convincing the respondents or participants. It is also a great challenge to make the participants comfortable when they talk in an interview. The 12th competency is *drawing conclusions from patterns and themes* which involves the difficulty of analyzing themes to create conclusion and integrating the generated themes in writing conclusion. Integrating the generated themes to conclusion requires analysis and synthesis; thus, it could be challenging to students to recognize the major themes and to form substantial synthesis in the conclusion. The ability to synthesize is one of the most essential and complex research skills. Yet, students have difficulty analyzing and synthesizing different pieces of information (Lundstrom et al. , 2010). The 13th competency is *describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc.)*. This comprises of the difficulty in reciting the characteristics of research. The difficulties encountered by the students in the 13th competency might be associated with their limited understanding about the characteristics of research since these are complex topics that may not be familiar to them. Also, in the slant of the difficulty encountered in reciting the characteristics of research, recitation has been really challenging to students because most of the time, students are overwhelmed by the pressure of sharing what they have understood from the lesson to their peers (Capriola, 2021). Lastly, the 14th competency is *creating patterns and themes from data*. This includes the difficulty encountered by the students in overviewing the data, coding the data, identifying

the patterns in the coded data, combining the codes to generate themes, reviewing the generated themes, and defining and naming themes. This may suggest that the students have a hard time organizing and categorizing data to create themes. The preceding result is greatly similar to the findings of Wang (2013) which specified that data analysis and organizing results are indeed very challenging processes for students; thus, they need to practice step-by-step procedure in analyzing qualitative data. The formal system for the qualitative data analysis involves vast coding, categorizing, and relating ideas or themes; so to avoid being overwhelmed with the process, the procedures in analyzing data must be done one step at a time. In the study of Connor (2017), he stated the detailed steps in analyzing qualitative data which include: 1) organizing the data, 2) finding and organizing ideas and concepts, 3) building broad themes in the data, 4) ensuring reliability and validity in the data analysis and the findings, and 5) finding possible and plausible explanations for findings. Taking conscious and precise steps in analyzing qualitative data could lessen students' stress and confusion in dealing with data. Consequently, the aforementioned difficulties could be categorized according to scientific and language difficulties; hence, the scientific difficulties encountered by students are defining the research process, identifying research gap; evaluation of theories, designs, and methods; utilizing research instruments; conducting data collection; analyzing qualitative data; and connecting findings to previous studies; while the language difficulties are using English vocabulary,

reading techniques (skimming, scanning, and critical reading), paraphrasing, summarizing, synthesizing, coherence, citation, referencing, verbal (English language) and non-verbal communication, and the ability to logically answer questions.

The 2nd major findings indicate that the difficulties encountered by students might be contributed by the following factors identified in the study which are: 1) *teaching instructions*, 2) *complexity of research parts*, 3) *time constraint*, 4) *insufficient resources*, 5.) *language skills*, 6) *lack of cooperation from group members*, and 7) *data gathering*. Among all factors, *teaching instructions* has the most number of occurrences, which may indicate that many of the students believe that teaching instructions, specifically the quality of discussion, explanation, and guidance given by the teacher in research class, could have greatly influenced the difficulties they experienced in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. This may also suggest that if the instruction from the teacher is insufficient, there is also the inadequacy of knowledge learned by students, which result in difficulty of *constructing research parts*. In the earlier study of Nind et al. (2019), he reiterated that in teaching research methods, it is important to acknowledge the difficulties, emotions, academic concerns, uncertainty, failure, and inadequacy of students while learning research, and they suggested the expansion of student-centered approaches in teaching research. Thus, effective instruction involves providing a good deal of instructional support by teaching new material in manageable amounts, modeling, guiding

student practice, helping students when they make errors, and providing sufficient practice and review (Rosenshine, 2012). In addition, *language skills* play a big factor in the difficulties encountered by students, specifically the written and oral application of the English language, which is comparable to the findings of Quazem & Zayid (2019). They concluded that the use of second language in writing research is one of the predominant challenges to students; thus, some students prefer to write research in their vernacular. Furthermore, underdeveloped oral communication skills contribute to the difficulty encountered by students because it affects their oral presentation which is also hampered by the fear of evaluation (Al-Nouh et al., 2015). Hence, language is a clear barrier between the student and their written and oral research tasks. Conversely, *complexity of research parts, time constraints, insufficient resources, lack of cooperation from the members, and data gathering* are factors that deal with the issues of difficulty on format and complexity, restricted or limited time, accessibility of free sources and materials, and more active cooperation. It must be accounted that writing as a process that really takes time and it is really a complex process. The notion is similar to the findings of Roxas (2020) in which he identified factors that contribute to the academic writing performance of students such as insufficient amount of reliable information because of limited resources and unique topics and time constraint in the writing process because of procrastinations due to the presence of several distractions.

Consistent with the hypothesis testing, the 3rd major findings showed a significant difference in the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 students in terms of their strands. The difficulties appeared to be significantly different between strands. Difficulty was manifested by the students in AUT, HRS, TRM, ABM, CSS, HSS, CPG, STM, and ELP; while the 2 strands DFT and EIM displayed neutrality. However, among the 9 strands that showed difficulty, the students from AUT, HRS, and TRM strands had the largest difficulty mean. The significant difference in the difficulties encountered by different strands was stressed on the large difficulty mean displayed by the students in the aforementioned strands. The significant difference in the difficulties encountered among strands might be contributed by the identified factors and it can be assumed that the students from the AUT, HRS, and TRM strands are more inclined to encounter difficulty in research than the students in other strands. Thus, the present findings appear to be similar to the foregoing research findings which claim that students from the non-academic track are observed to have difficulties in coping with academic matters because of their negative attitude towards academic involvement (Houtte & Stevens, 2009). Also, in a previous study, academic track obtained above average scores in the scholastic test compared to non-academic track that obtained average score (Almirino et al., 2020). Thus, the large difficulty of the 3 strands might be associated to the subject specialization of different tracks wherein the subject specialization of non-academic track is more focused on livelihood skills than academic

skills. Therefore, the non-academic track is less exposed to academic skills compared to the academic track where the specialization focuses on the academic skills such as language, mathematics, and science (Development Asia, 2019). So, students from non-academic track should be given extra support and intervention in the learning process.

Accordingly, the present study found that the Grade 11 students encountered difficulties in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 specifically in the 1) *oral presentation of the written research report*, 2) *finalizing research output*, 3) *knowing the search process (choose research topic, identify research problem, develop research questions, create research design, write proposal)*, 4) *selecting relevant literature*, 5) *writing coherent review of literature*, 6) *presenting vast review*, 7) *synthesizing information from relevant literature*, 8) *relating the research findings with pertinent literature*, 9) *writing research methodology (research design, locale, population, sample size, data gathering method, etc.)*, 10) *planning data collection and analysis procedures*, 11) *utilizing materials and techniques to produce creative research output*, 12) *drawing conclusions from patterns and themes*, 13) *describing characteristics of research (empirical, logical, cyclical, analytical, etc.)*, and 14) *creating patterns and themes from data*. The particular difficulties encountered by the students in the aforementioned learning competencies could be categorized according to scientific and language difficulties; hence, the scientific difficulties encountered by students are defining the research process;

identifying research gap, evaluation of theories, designs, and methods; utilizing research instruments; conducting data collection; analyzing qualitative data; and connecting findings to previous studies; while the language difficulties are using English vocabulary, reading techniques (skimming, scanning, and critical reading), paraphrasing, summarizing, synthesizing, coherence, citation, referencing, verbal (English language) and non-verbal communication, and ability to logically answer questions. Also, the difficulties manifested by students in each of the 14 difficult learning competencies could be contributed by factors which are related to teaching instructions, complexity of research parts, time constraint, insufficient resources, language skills, lack of cooperation from group members, and data gathering. The findings of this study have relevantly shown that the students who experience large difficulties in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 are from the AUT, HRS, and TRM strands. This may indicate that students from AUT, HRS, and TRM strands are more likely to encounter difficulties compared to the students from other strands because the 3 strands have the largest difficulty mean among all participating strands.

Proposed Instructional Model for Practical Research 1

The instructional model for teaching Practical Research 1 is proposed to respond to the major difficulties (scientific and language) encountered by Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. The model is comprised of the ideal

teaching instruction for the course, learning needs assessment, and subject integration since these are the major factors of difficulties identified in the findings of the present study.

Figure 2. An Instructional Model for Teaching Practical Research 1

Practical Research 1 has a list of learning competencies (knowledge or skills) that are projected to be acquired or demonstrated by the students at the end of the course. The Department of Education previously revised Practical Research 1 curriculum guide in

the year 2020, which reduced the 36 learning competencies to 30 Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC's). These 30 most essential learning competencies are the combination of scientific and language learning competencies. At present, the revised curriculum guide with 30 MELC's is the basis of teaching Practical Research 1. Before implementing the revised guide, the learning needs of students were assessed to identify their strength and weaknesses on the list of learning competencies and to know which learning competencies would be given much focus. The major findings identified that the Grade 11 students encountered difficulties in the learning competencies of research, mainly in the 14 out of 36 learning competencies. The identified difficulties were categorized to scientific and language difficulties. The difficulties encountered by the students in the scientific learning competencies were defining the research process, identifying research gap, evaluation of theories, designs, and methods, utilizing research instruments, conducting data collection, analyzing qualitative data, and connecting findings to previous studies; while the difficulties in they encountered in the language learning competencies in English were vocabulary, reading techniques (skimming, scanning, and critical reading), paraphrasing, summarizing, synthesizing, coherence, citation, referencing, verbal (English language) and non-verbal communication, ability to logically answer questions. Consequently, the major factors that contributed to the difficulties were teaching instruction which was described as insufficient in discussion and explanation, language skills of

students, and complexity of research parts. With the identified difficulties and factors, the present study proposes a model for teaching Practical Research 1 which encompasses *Learning Needs Assessment (Scientific and Language)*, *Direct Instruction*, and *Subject Integration* as the instructional interventions to help students cope with the encountered difficulties.

The proposed teaching model is a response to the vital difficulties encountered by the students in Practical Research 1 and the factors that contribute to the difficulties, specifically the difficulty in understanding, doing, and writing the complex research parts and processes. The instructional model uses the Practical Research 1 MELC's as the teacher's guide to identify the overall coverage of the course, including the learning competencies and the course content. In the proposed model, the learning needs of the students in all learning competencies (scientific and language needs) are identified first by the teacher through the *Learning Needs Assessment* before proceeding to instruction. Its purpose is basically to respond to the scientific and language needs of students in the written and oral presentation of research. The Learning needs assessment is described as a systematic approach to examine the state of knowledge, ability, interest, or attitude of the students about the course (McCawley, 2004). It would help the teacher to identify the learning competencies that are difficult for students, which should be given more focus in the teaching instruction. The *Direct Learning Needs Assessment* type could be utilized in

identifying the learning needs of students. This type of learning needs assessment involves looking at the actual performance of students in test or sample work (Allmen et al., 2021). There should be an assessment tool to conduct a direct learning needs assessment. This learning needs assessment tool could be a teacher-made test that covers the identified difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of the course, specifically in the scientific and language learning competencies. In constructing the assessment tool, the findings about the particular difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies should be the main content of the tool. The assessment tool should encompass the difficulties in scientific learning competencies which are defining the research process; identifying research gap; evaluation of theories, designs, and methods; utilizing research instruments; conducting data collection; analyzing qualitative data; and connecting findings to previous studies; and also the difficulties in the language learning competencies which are English vocabulary, reading techniques (skimming, scanning, and critical reading), paraphrasing, summarizing, synthesizing, coherence, citation, referencing, verbal (English language) and non-verbal communication, and ability to logically answer questions. Subsequently, the assessment tool should reflect the strengths and weaknesses of the students in the said competencies. The results of the direct learning needs assessment could serve as the focal points or the central competencies that need to be highlighted and reiterated by the teacher during the instruction for students' mastery of

the competencies.

When the scientific and language learning needs are already identified in the direct learning needs assessment, an explicit instruction should be applied for the students to easily grasp the identified difficult competencies. Hence, the *Direct Instruction* should be applied to accommodate the learning needs of students. The direct instruction aimed to address the difficulties experienced by students in the scientific and language learning competencies of research such as the overwhelming process of data collection, data coding, synthesizing, evaluating, writing research parts, etc., which are primarily contributed by the implicit and insufficient teaching instructions. Conversely, Direct Instruction is a teaching theory comprising explicit teaching instruction wherein the teacher uses modeling to demonstrate the desired skills or concept (Renard, 2019). This instruction is opposite to the common practice in the research locale, according to the findings, and it comprises of 6 basic phases which are 1) *Introduction or Review*. The teacher must set the stage for learning by connecting prior knowledge to the present topic or by primarily connecting the research topic to the consciousness or schema of students; 2) *Development*. The teacher should model the expected outcomes (research title, statement of the problem, etc.) by providing a clear lecture or demonstration of the desired skills or concepts while students learn by observing. The use of first language, examples, visuals, read aloud, and graphic organizer are some of the suggested instructional supports in the development phase; 3)

Guided Practice. After modeling the concept or skills, the teacher should monitor and engage students with assigned learning tasks then provide meaningful feedback. Students could work in a group while performing the guided practice that could serve as a *scaffolding* strategy to help struggling students cope with the difficult concepts or tasks; 4) *Closure.* The teacher must summarize the lesson by highlighting the important concepts and skills that are covered; 5) *Independent Practice.* Since the students have already experienced the guided task, this time, the teacher should provide individual learning tasks that are independent of teacher and peer assistance; and 6) *Evaluation.* The teacher must assess students' progress by comparing the initial grade or ability of students (identified in the *Learning Needs Assessment* and the *Guided Practice*) with the final grade or ability of students after the instruction. If the grade or ability of the student does not improve in the evaluation stage, the student may be given another guided task. This kind of instruction has been found effective in teaching students with learning difficulties (Elik & Sali, 2016; Witt, 2018). Also, it improves the learning outcomes of students who have low learning motivation (Winarsih, 2019). Hence, it could help the students in learning the difficult scientific and language learning competencies of research because it has step-by-step demonstration, modelling, and scaffolding which could be effective to support learning.

Furthermore, integrating the topics and learning competencies of two separate courses could help in supporting the learning needs of students especially their language

needs. Integration is defined as the process of combining two or more things effectively (Cambridge Dictionary, 2021). Thus, *Subject Integration* assimilated in the model could be described as combining two or more subjects to reinforce the learning needs of students aside from giving them direct instructions. The inclusion of subject integration in the model aims to empower the language skills of students which have been found as huge barrier in accomplishing and mastering the learning competencies. The idea of subject integration is anchored on *Interdisciplinary Approach*, which allows the students to learn by making connections between concepts and learning competencies across varied disciplines (Appleby, 2015). This subject integration could only address the language needs of students and could not be applicable on the scientific learning needs of students in research because only the Grade 11 English subjects have suitable and related learning competencies that could be integrated in Practical Research 1, and contrary there is that there is no Grade 11 science subject that could be merged to the scientific learning competencies of Practical Research1. Consequently, this subject integration is more focused in reinforcing the language needs of students which are identified in the language learning needs assessment. Specifically, the language needs assessment would focus on assessing the identified difficult language areas of research such as English vocabulary, reading techniques (skimming, scanning, and critical reading), paraphrasing, summarizing, synthesizing, coherence, citation, referencing, verbal (English language) and non-verbal communication,

and ability to logically answer questions. The language learning needs assessment tool could be a teacher-made test that could identify the strengths and weaknesses of students on the afore-mentioned language learning needs. After the research teacher has identified the language needs of students, the list of identified language needs should be reported to their Grade 11 language teachers, specifically to the Reading and Writing, and Oral Communication teachers. Subsequently, English teachers should give extra learning input or support to the language learning needs of students by incorporating or highlighting the needed knowledge or skills in the language course. Practical Research 1 and language subjects should conduct separate discussion using direct instruction on each of the language learning needs of students to strengthen the knowledge and skills of students in research writing. Then, the evaluation of students' progress in their language needs could be separately or jointly conducted by the language and research teachers at the end of every language learning competency. On the other hand, collaborative evaluation is ideal to provide wide learning scope for students and to lessen the number of evaluation that the students need to take in the aforesaid courses. Thus, there should be keen cooperation and clear communication between the research teacher and language teacher to successfully apply the subject integration. Moreover, only the related learning competencies should be integrated into the language courses to avoid interference with the main objectives of the separate courses.

Conceivably, this proposed instructional model for teaching Practical Research 1 could help the students cope with the identified learning difficulties. This could primarily identify the learning needs of students on the scientific and language learning competencies of the research course based on the present findings. Then, the identified learning needs could serve as the focal competencies that should be given extra time and repetition for it to be mastered by students. These learning needs could be supported by direct instruction and subject integration. Consequently, the model encourages focused and supportive instruction in teaching Practical Research 1, which aims to help the students cope with the difficulties they encounter in the course and eventually to master the learning competencies of the course.

Conclusion

Practical Research 1, which is a qualitative type research, is one of the subjects offered in Grade 11. This course consists of learning competencies that need to be learned and mastered by the Grade 11 students. The learning competencies of Practical Research 1 are skill-based that should be acquired by students after finishing the course because it is anchored on the Competency-Based Education of the K to 12 Curriculum. In some cases, students encounter difficulties in the specified learning competencies of the research course given the fact that they are novice researchers. It is important to identify if the given competencies are attainable by students and if there are difficulties encountered while

dealing with the learning competencies. Identifying the students' learning needs is helpful for them to be given differentiated support. Thus, this study focused on knowing the difficulties encountered by students in the learning competencies of research and the factors that contribute to the difficulties. Also, it aimed to provide recommendations and instructional model that could help students cope with the identified difficulties. Consequently, the major findings of the present study on the difficulties encountered by the Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 reinforce the succeeding conclusion.

Primarily, the Grade 11 students experienced difficulty in the 14 out of 36 learning competencies of Practical Research 1, specifically the students in AUT, HRS, TRM, ABM, CSS, HSS, CPG, STM, and ELP. However, the students from AUT, HRS, and TRM strands had the largest difficulty mean among the 9 strands who manifested difficulty. Based on the findings, the major factor that contribute to the difficulties encountered by students is *teaching instruction* described by students as having insufficient explanation on the research topics and technical terms and lack of demonstration of the actual research writing. Presumably, every student can learn well if he or she receives adequate instruction. Based on the study of Hattie (as cited in Effective Instruction Overview, 2021), better learning happens when teachers offer explicit instruction than inactive instruction which focuses on content. Thus, to withstand the difficulties encountered by students in the course which are

primarily contributed by the teaching instruction, the utilization of *Direct Instruction* is assumed to be helpful. According to Renard (2019), Direct Instruction is a teaching theory that posits explicit teaching instruction wherein the teacher uses modeling to demonstrate the desired skills or concepts. It comprises of 6 basic phases which are: 1) *Introduction or Review*. Set stage for learning by connecting prior knowledge to the present topic; 2) *Development*. Model the expected outcomes by providing a clear lecture or demonstration of the desired skills or concepts while students learn by observing. The use of first language, examples, visuals, read aloud, and graphic organizer are some of the suggested instructional supports in the development phase; 3) *Guided Practice*. Monitor and engage students with assigned learning tasks then provide meaningful feedback. Students could work in a group while performing the guided practice that could serve as a strategy to help struggling students cope with the difficult concepts or tasks; 4) *Closure*. Bring the lesson to a conclusion by highlighting what is covered; 5) *Independent Practice*. Provide individual learning tasks that are independent of teacher assistance; 6) *Evaluation*. Assess pupil progress. Consequently, Direct Instruction Theory is anchored on the *Social Learning Theory* of Bandura, which asserts that most human behavior is learned through observation, imitation, and modeling new behavior patterns and cognitive competencies (Kurt, 2020), and *the Scaffolding Theory* of Vygotsky, which highlights helpful strategies on how learners achieve independence by working in collaboration with a skilled instructor or more

knowledgeable peers who could help them make connections between concepts. Scaffolding also uses a variety of support such as models, visuals, and hints for the students to progress on a task (Williams, 2020). The 2 mentioned learning theories are the foundation of Direct Instruction Theory. In the current years, direct instruction is positively recommended by recently conducted studies. It has been found effective in teaching students with learning difficulties (Elik & Sali, 2016; Witt, 2018). Also, it improves the learning outcomes of students who have low learning motivation (Winarsih, 2019). Though this learning instruction is believed to be traditional, its efficiency is still proven in modern times. Thus, direct instruction is ideal in research teaching especially to the students who display difficulties in research writing since this kind of instruction provides modeling and scaffolding. Moreover, the use of direct instruction through modeling the process of writing the complex research parts and supporting learning difficulties would help the students acquire the anticipated learning competencies.

Furthermore, *time constraint* is another factor that contributes to the difficulty encountered by the Grade 11 students. This is also a vital factor because it hinders teachers to teach the lesson profoundly and it limits the time of students to internalize their learning. This may be a product of the congested K to 12 Curriculum. In line with the view on congested K to 12 Curriculum, Senator Win Gachalian, the Chairman of Senate Committee on Basic Education, called for its urgent reform (Senate of the Philippines, 2020).

Accordingly, the time constraint experienced by students in Practical Research 1 is an effect of the congested curriculum. Practical Research 1 consists of 34 learning competencies that need to be acquired by students within the duration of 80 learning hours, so there are only 2.35 hours per learning competency, which is insufficient especially to the complex learning competencies such as writing the research title, related literature, and methodology. Thus, to avoid congestion, the only way is either to lessen the learning competencies or to add more learning hours. Certainly, adding more learning hours to accommodate the desired course competencies would hugely affect the entire K to 12 Curriculum, which might add burden than gain to the education stakeholders. Perhaps, the last resort is to lessen the learning competencies by concentrating on the most essential learning competencies of Practical Research 1. Recently, in the mid of 2020, DepEd released the implementation of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in all the K to 12 subjects, including Practical Research 1. According to DepEd (2020), the MELCs is not only a response to the new normal education brought by the COVID-19 pandemic but it is also part of the ongoing reform of the K to 12 Curriculum to provide a more resilient education. Grounded on the implementation of MELCs, the original 36 learning competencies of Practical Research 1 are reduced to 30 Most Essential Learning Competencies, which means that every learning competency should be learned within 2.67 learning hours. Nevertheless, the 30 most essential competencies still seem congested for

the 80 hours duration. Most of the student respondents reiterated that 1 semester (80 hours) is inadequate to accomplish all the learning competencies of the course, so it may be a good notion to make the learning competencies more concise. On the other hand, it could be an alternative strategy to implement subject integration when it is impossible to reduce the learning competencies. Integration is defined as the process of combining two or more things effectively (Cambridge Dictionary, 2021). Thus, subject integration means bringing the interrelated subjects together. The idea of subject integration is anchored on *Interdisciplinary Approach*, which allows the students to learn by making connections between concepts and learning competencies across varied disciplines (Appleby, 2015), for instance, integrating Practical Research 1 to Reading and Writing. Since some of the learning competencies of Practical Research 1 focus on writing strategies such as paraphrasing and synthesizing, then those learning competencies could be integrated into similar competencies in Reading and Writing. Both subjects work on the students' acquisition of the learning competencies and encourage connection between courses, which could help reinforce the skills or knowledge of students in a limited time. The integrated subjects could also collaborate in activities to lessen the tasks of students. Consequently, subject integration could be a helpful strategy to address the time constraint. It could not only lessen the tasks of students and teachers but could also reinforce the knowledge and skills of students in a congested curriculum.

Lastly, the Grade 11 students encountered difficulties in the language learning competencies of Practical Research 1, which indicates that they are not confident with their *language skills*, specifically in the written and oral presentation of research. Thus, *Language Needs Assessment* should be conducted to identify the students' language strengths and weaknesses. Language needs assessment intends to identify gaps or areas in the language skills or knowledge of students that needs to be improved (Verner, 2021). Hence, identifying the gap is necessary because it would determine the types of content that should be focally taught to fill students' language needs. The needs assessment would focus on assessing the identified difficult language areas in Practical Research 1 such as using English vocabulary, reading techniques (skimming, scanning, and critical reading), paraphrasing, summarizing, synthesizing, coherence, citation, referencing, verbal (English language) and non-verbal communication, and the ability to logically answer questions. A simple language needs assessment tool (academic essay, objective test, oral presentation activity, and performance checklist, etc.) could be developed by the teacher which should be based on the identified difficulties encountered by students in the scientific and language learning competencies of Practical Research 1. Afterward, an instructional intervention should be utilized to address the identified language needs of students. Instructional intervention helps students to progress on their learning needs. It could be a specific program or set of steps to support the specific learning needs of students and it could last

certain weeks or months (Lee, 2021). In light of the instructional intervention, the present study proposed that after the language assessment in Practical Research 1, the list of identified language needs should be endorsed to the Grade 11 language courses, specifically Reading and Writing and Oral Communication courses. With the use of *Subject Integration*, the language teachers should address the identified language needs of students by incorporating and highlighting the needed skill or knowledge in the language course. The subject integration could serve as the instructional intervention that might be helpful to reinforce the language needs of students. Conversely, the evaluation of students' progress could be evaluated by the research teacher or both the research teacher and language teacher at the end of every language learning competency. Thus, there should be a keen collaboration and clear communication between the research teacher and language teacher to successfully apply the subject integration as intervention. In addition, only the related topics or activities should be integrated into the language courses to avoid interference with the main objectives of the separate courses.

Recommendations

The findings of the study specify some difficulties encountered by the Grade 11 students in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1. Anchored on the Competency-based Education, the main product of the learning process should be the students' successful demonstration of the learning competencies so students should receive

timely differentiated support according to their individual needs or learning difficulties. Also, the principle of Competency-Based Language Teaching should be applied to the identified difficulties vital to language learning. This CBLT principle necessitates teachers to assess the language needs of students at the beginning and end of the course. Given the fact that the difficulties encountered by students could make their chance of success low (Ajzen, 1985), these difficulties or learning needs could be used as the basis to provide support to students to be successful in the demonstration of the learning competencies.

The present study which is grounded on the previous findings and relevant theories proposed the following recommendations to help the students cope with the encountered difficulties in the learning competencies of Practical Research 1:

1. *Direct Instruction* should be utilized when teaching Practical Research 1, especially with struggling students. The afore-mentioned instruction has been proven effective in teaching students with learning difficulties (Elik & Sali, 2016; Witt, 2018), hence it may be helpful to the students who display difficulties in the learning competencies (scientific and language) of Practical Research 1. Besides, using direct instruction could improve the students' understanding of complex research parts and process of research by providing a good deal of instructional support, teaching new concepts in a manageable amount, modeling, guiding student practice, helping students when they made errors, and providing sufficient practice and

review.

2. Given the fact that the Grade 11 students encountered difficulty in the language learning competencies of Practical Research 1 such as using English vocabulary, reading techniques (skimming, scanning, and critical reading), paraphrasing, summarizing, synthesizing, coherence, citation, referencing, verbal (English language) and non-verbal communication, and the ability to logically answer questions, the language needs of students should be assessed by the research teacher at the beginning of the course using a teacher-made tool (essay test, objective test, interview, etc.) which focuses on the desired language learning competencies in Practical Research. Subsequently, after identifying the language needs of students, integration of students' language course and research course should be implemented to address language learning needs. The language course could be the one to reinforce the language needs of students. Hence, the subject integration would serve as the instructional intervention to help students cope with the language learning difficulties identified in the needs assessment. However, the final evaluation of the students' language progress should be evaluated by the research teacher after the discussion of the language learning competencies in Practical Research 1.
3. One of the identified factors that contributed to the difficulties encountered by students is the unavailability of credible and free sources. As a result, students

struggled in searching for relevant literature. Thus, the research teacher, as well as the school library, should assist students in finding reliable and free sources or even provide students with available links for free journal publications or other relevant online resources. This may reduce the time that students might spend in searching relevant sources and the frustration they may experience.

4. Since the students encountered difficulties when working in a group for the reason that some members are too dependent on the group leader, teachers should ensure the collaboration of members within groups. A checklist of cooperation validated by the group leader could be used for monitoring member's participation.
5. Grade 11 students are considered novice research writers because of their little to no knowledge about research writing when they enroll in the course. Based on the findings, one of the factors that contributed to the students' difficulties is their insufficient knowledge about some terminologies, parts of research, and the importance of research. Consequently, to address this factor, the school must organize seminars about the relevance, basic aspects, and methods of qualitative research to reinforce the knowledge of students about research and must initiate research fairs to encourage a research-oriented learning environment.
6. Curriculum developers must revisit the Practical Research 1 curriculum guide, including the list of learning competencies and the estimated time to perform or

accomplish the competencies to address the problem of time constraints.

7. The use of *Direct Instruction* and *Subject Integration* is proposed in the study to respond to the identified difficulties and factors encountered by Grade 11 students; thus, further study about the effectiveness of the abovementioned instructional interventions could be pursued by the future researchers.

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